

HeriTACE

Cultural heritage analysis and value assessment

Deliverable D5.2

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Executive Summary

The transition towards climate neutrality by 2050, as envisioned by the European Green Deal and the New European Bauhaus, requires a profound transformation of the built environment. One of the key challenges in this process is the sustainable renovation of the European housing stock, particularly in historic cities, where heritage preservation must be carefully balanced with climate goals. In this context, the HeriTACE project addresses the question of how-to future-proof small to medium-sized heritage townhouses – specifically those built before 1945 – while respecting their cultural significance.

Deliverable D5.2: Cultural Heritage Analysis and Value Assessment is part of the HeriTACE project's Work Package 5 (*Holistic and Multi-Scale Renovation Approach for Heritage Townhouses in Historical Neighbourhoods*), and specifically Subtask T5.1.1 – *Cultural Heritage Analysis*, coordinated by Politecnico di Milano. This deliverable focuses on the development and application of a consistent methodology for assessing the cultural values of historic buildings, with the aim of supporting renovation strategies that are compatible with their heritage significance. A key challenge lies in the absence of a unified European methodology for evaluating the significance of built heritage, especially in the context of energy retrofit interventions.

To address this gap, the research team developed a standardised assessment document/tool titled the **"Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building."** This two-part document includes:

- A **Building Identity Card**, which gathers objective, technical, and contextual information (e.g., geometry, location, protection constraints, materials, architectural components, state of conservation of elements, etc.);
- A **Building Values Assessment**, which introduces structured criteria to evaluate the historic building's aesthetic, architectural, historical, scientific, cultural, and social significance.

The approach is grounded in European standards (particularly EN 16883:2017) and builds on the idea that value-based assessment is a prerequisite for any renovation plan that aims to be both sustainable and culturally respectful. By recognising both protected and non-protected buildings with heritage character, the methodology supports decision-making even in cases where legal protection instruments are absent or insufficient.

The Summary Sheet was tested on **23 case studies** across four countries – Belgium, Estonia, Italy, and Norway – selected to represent a wide range of climates, construction traditions, and regulatory frameworks. Testing involved collaboration between research institutions and heritage authorities, allowing for a nuanced understanding of local typologies and contexts. The goal of this testing phase was to verify whether the tool could produce reliable and transferable results across diverse European conditions.

The findings, presented in Sections 2-5 of this report, confirm that the Summary Sheet provides a consistent yet flexible framework for identifying the heritage value of historic buildings. This value-based analysis can effectively inform renovation strategies, aligning them with the cultural identity of each building.

Despite differences among the case studies – particularly in terms of materials, structural systems, conservation states, and functional transformations – the tool revealed clear

correlations between building typologies, perceived heritage value, and the degree of transformation over time.

The **main takeaways** of this activity include:

- The successful creation and calibration of a replicable heritage value assessment tool suitable for different European contexts;
- The development of a comprehensive, structured dataset of townhouse features and typologies to support future archetype-based analysis;
- The recognition that common typological elements (e.g., timber floors, masonry walls, decorated façades) are adapted in different ways depending on local culture, protection levels, and renovation histories.

These insights directly inform the Deliverable D5.4, which defines pre-renovation baseline scenarios for selected archetypes – an essential reference for upcoming retrofit planning.

Finally, the conclusions of this report highlight the broader value of this work. By integrating technical data collection with structured heritage assessment, the summary sheet supports the creation of a multi-dimensional evaluation framework. This is a crucial step toward developing retrofit strategies that account not only for energy and structural performance but also for the cultural significance of historic townhouses.

As part of the overall HeriTACE methodology, the outcomes of this research are expected to feed directly into the work of WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP6, and to complement insights on user interaction and perception explored in Deliverable D5.3.

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AGA	Annotated Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of the Action - annex 1 to the GA
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HEU	Horizon Europe
HV	Heritage Value
ICOMOS	International Council on Monuments and Sites
PMT	Project management team
PO	Project officer
UNESCO	The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
RP	Reporting period
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The ambitions of the European Union (EU) are substantial: to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. The European Green Deal and the New European Bauhaus aim to succeed a sustainable and inclusive society through transdisciplinary collaboration and innovation. The necessity and value of sustainable use and transformation of existing built environment has been emphasized in research for a long time (Fufa et al., 2022). However, one of the most significant challenges in this transition will be the renovation wave of our housing stock, which accounts for 27% of the final energy use of the EU (Eurostat, 2025). Historic cities in Europe present an additional difficulty. It is evident that the historically valuable buildings in these cities must be preserved while respecting and considering the inherent heritage and societal values. However, the methods for achieving this while maintaining climate neutrality are often less clear.

According to the need of bridging the gap between built heritage conservation needs and environmental ambitions, the HeriTACE project investigates how we can future proof our heritage buildings in a well-balanced manner. The project focuses specifically on achieving the ambitious goal of climate-neutrality in small to medium-sized heritage townhouses pre-dating 1945. The project therefore takes into consideration groups of buildings that are not only officially protected, but buildings that more generally have a recognizable “heritage value”.

Built heritage value assessment is a crucial activity in the retrofitting process from a conservation perspective. It can guide decision-makers, even in cases where legal protection is absent or does not address all the specific characteristics of a building—features that may nonetheless be significant for preservation. However, the definition of “heritage value” and the methods by which it can be assessed remain subjects of ongoing debate. This issue lies at the heart of discussions on heritage management and often raises controversial questions, such as which elements of the built heritage should be preserved, conserved, restored, maintained, renovated, or potentially made available for reuse or reconstruction. Key questions that continue to prompt discussion include what aspects of our built heritage should be regarded as ‘valuable’ and why; what value the built heritage adds to society/cultural context; how valuable built heritage is both in absolute terms and in relative terms.

The value of built heritage, and more importantly how that value should be defined, is thus an issue deserving academic and practical attention. Nevertheless, there is currently no unified European standard detailing how heritage significance should be evaluated, and procedures vary widely across Europe and internationally.

In recent years, a push on the topic has been given by the publication of the EN 16883:2017 “Conservation of cultural heritage - Guidelines for improving the energy performance of historic buildings”. Indeed, this standard provides a structured framework to gather data on various aspects of a historic building's knowledge profile, including its heritage value, construction, systems, materials, and energy usage. The cultural heritage significance is considered pivotal in this document, and it's described as “combination of all the heritage values assigned to a building and its setting” (as indicated in the EN 15898:2011, 3.1.6); the term heritage value it is considered as “an aspect of importance that individuals or society

assign(s) to a building". Hence, the heritage significance process suggested in the EN 16883 is considered as a statement of elements value.

Following the principles outlined in this standard, the purpose of this report is to show the results of the research work carried out within the HeriTACE project workpackage WP5 - *Holistic and Multi-Scale Renovation Approach for Heritage Townhouses in Historical Neighbourhoods*, specifically under Subtask T5.1.1 - *Cultural Heritage Analysis*, coordinated by Politecnico di Milano.

The conducted research aimed to answer to two combined needs:

- to develop a system capable of supporting decision-makers in efficiently compiling building knowledge data relevant to a historic building under analysis;
- to enable the assessment of the heritage significance of a historic building using simple, shareable criteria applicable across different contexts and countries, including at the neighbourhood scale.

As part of this effort, a technical document titled "*Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building*" has been developed to facilitate the systematic collection and storage of data, particularly in the context of energy retrofit interventions. This document is twofold and includes a Building Identity Card section that gathers key objective data – such as building geometry, applicable constraints, and more – alongside a structured guidance for assessing a broad range of heritage values (Building Values Assessment section), including aesthetic, architectural, historical, scientific, cultural, experiential, and social dimensions, for a comprehensive understanding of heritage assets. The contents of this outcome are explained in Section 1 of this report. The developed summary sheet describes the results of the historic building analysis as part of WP5 of the HeriTACE research project. A more technical description of the building and building systems of the case-study building to support the modelling work WP2-3-4 it thought to be made in parallel to this document in D2.1, D3.2 and D4.1 of the HeriTACE project, while in the D5.3 more information about users' impact on heritage value assessment are provided. These studies serve as a complement and background to this report.

To test the effectiveness of this tool in capturing the specific characteristics and values of historic buildings across different contexts and countries, project partners applied the developed sheet to a selection of historic buildings chosen as case studies in their respective countries (Belgium, Norway, Estonia, and Italy) (more information about the selected case studies are provided in D5.1). The results of this application are presented in Sections 2-5.

Finally, the Conclusions section of this report illustrates how the simultaneous use of this data collection system in four European partner countries – supported by governmental authorities responsible for the protection and preservation of cultural heritage – led to the identification of important exploitation results, useful to reach the goal of the project in developing a multidimensional holistic approach, contributing also to define the reference situation for the HeriTACE archetypical case studies renovation (reported in D5.4).

2. Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building

Authors: Alessia Buda (PoliMI), Valeria Pracchi (PoliMI)

This document is twofold and includes a Building Identity Card section that gathers key objective data – such as building geometry, applicable constraints, and more – alongside a structured guidance for assessing a broad range of heritage values (Building Values Assessment section), including aesthetic, architectural, historical, scientific, cultural, experiential, and social dimensions, for a comprehensive understanding of heritage assets.

2.1. Building Identity Card

To assess the building heritage significance, EN 16883 (paragraph 7.3 *Describing heritage significance and conservation opportunities and constraints*) recommends conducting a building analysis that should cover all parts of the construction and is informed by its historical development. It should include information such as the historic building urban context, its protection restrictions, the asset geometry, its architectural peculiarities, valuable elements and beyond, detecting also the state of conservation of each building component. The methods of recording and documentation produced should be appropriate and proportionate to the nature of the building and its heritage significance and for the purpose of the recording.

According to the EN 16883 guidelines suggestions, the first section of the “Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building” is designed as a flexible and guided checklist. The sheet also takes its cue from the technical regulatory literature aimed at establishing the purposes and context relating to the description of the state of conservation for movable cultural heritage (such as EN 16095:2012) and immovable cultural heritage (such as EN 16096:2012). The sheet establishes, as indicated in the standards, how the state of conservation of the built cultural heritage subject to energy renovation must be examined, documented and recorded. It therefore includes the assessment of the state of conservation of the building on the basis of visual observation, accompanied, when necessary, by simple measurements. It adapts to the specific goals of individual building surveys, indicating for each required data field the appropriate data collection methods and any relevant descriptive formats. Its simplified approach to data gathering supports a comprehensive understanding of the building and is intended to be applicable in a variety of situations—especially where constraints or limited resources restrict the scope of the survey.

This section covers the following areas of knowledge (Figures 1-4):

- **General information:** it includes a short description of the building, author/architect, original and current function, construction period, typology, and bibliographic/web references. history and development of the building and its elements, construction details, technical building systems, etc. This includes also the original design, sequential development of exterior and interior form and evolving use or function of the building. It requires at the end to add full-width image of the property, aerial view showing solar orientation;

- **Geographical/Administrative location:** this is an information collection on country, region, province, city, address, cadastral data;
- **Climatic Conditions:** it includes a climate classification based on Köppen system, the Heating/Cooling Degree Days, a short description of façade orientation in relation to sun/wind and to indicate the presence of specific climate data files;
- **Urban Context:** it asks to describe the historical development of the urban context of the building by analysing historical maps showing the building transformation, then the description of the current context (city centre, coastal area, etc.), access routes to the building and notes on trees/buildings casting shadows on the property;
- **Ownership and Legal Constraints:** this collects indications on ownership (public/private/mixed), stakeholders and management roles, legal heritage status and applicable laws, inclusion of the building in protected areas (e.g., UNESCO), rules and permissions for interventions;
- **Architectural Characteristics:** it asks for data on geometry, number of floors, presence of extensions, basements, attics, description of heated/unheated areas and volumes, surface/volume ratio. For a better understanding of the building architecture, some drawings should be added;
- **Construction Elements:** This section of the building identity card focuses on documenting, as thoroughly as possible based on the knowledge acquired, the construction characteristics of the historic building. For this reason, this section is divided into smaller subsections, as follows.
 - **Structural system:** This subsection requires information on the foundations, load-bearing systems, and construction materials. It should also include any visible defects affecting the stability of structural elements, as well as any known past retrofitting interventions. Additional details may cover distinctive structural features related to local building traditions (e.g., decorated pillars, structurally innovative solutions for the time, or original materials). The description can also note the presence of historical structural details, including reinforcement systems such as anchors;
 - **Building Envelope Components:** This subsection aims to provide detailed information on the various components of the building envelope, including roofs, walls, floors, ceilings, openings, and shading systems. For each element, the description should include its type, construction features, material composition, state of conservation, and any presence of decorative or valuable elements. Sketches and photographs must be provided for each component to document different typologies, finishes, and decorative details.
 - **Interiors:** this subsection asks to describe different interior spaces architectural and valuable peculiarities per room. For facilitating this operation, it is suggested to adopt a simplified "Raumbuch" method (room

book): starting from the single floor plan per building level, rooms can be identified with a code. Once the room has been identified, it can be virtually broken down into its six main faces: ceiling, floor and the four walls. For each architectural component, all constructive and decorative elements (e.g., openings stringcourse frames, finishing as tapestries, fireplaces, decorations, etc) are described briefly in their material, technical and conservative characteristics. This section can be also linked to the previous description sections.

- **Technical Installations:** this part asks for general information about past and present technical installations. This can include a summary of past energy efficiency interventions carried out on the building, available energy documentation (reports, certificates, utility bills), data on occupancy (number of people, usage schedules), a survey of electrical components and a brief description of the HVAC systems. Other installations as DHW (Domestic Hot Water), renewables and passive systems and strategies (e.g. ventilation ducts, ventilation tower, etc.) may also be described here.

The building identity card concludes with a summary of the overall state of conservation. It is recommended to identify any building pathologies and, where possible, their causes (e.g., issues related to water such as infiltration or rising damp; or comfort-related problems such as air leaks, poor ventilation, presence of harmful substances, or absence of shading systems). A short description of the condition of existing technical installations—including passive systems—should also be included, indicating whether they are still in use and any problems observed. This information should be supported with photographs and annotated drawings where applicable.

D5.2 Cultural heritage analysis and value assessment

GENERAL INFORMATION		Comments
Building general description		
<p>Building from the early 17th century, it corresponds to the typology of the Palazzetto. With three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic, the building has a three-openings rhythm on the facade, without presenting any other decoration. The building planimetry is developed in depth. The structure is made of solid bricks with exposed wooden floors and a sloping roof with ancient wooden trusses. At the top, there is an open turret with an ancient wooden double pitch roof structure and small openings on the top of the walls, which help to ventilate and bring more light into the rooms. An internal courtyard/garden at the back allows the rooms to gain more sunlight.</p> <p>The vertical distribution takes place via an historical staircase in stone located in the middle of the lot. In the middle of the building planimetry there is an atrium which is now glazed, but which was once open to the outside and allowed the sun to enter the rooms: two historic windows, with ancient glass panels bound in lead alloy, embedded in the masonry, testify this ancient use of the internal atrium. The rooms are mostly frescoed and the plaster false ceiling has a reed grip structure underneath. Many of the windows were replaced in the 80s with wooden frames and double glazing.</p>		
<i>Bibliography: insert here the main references if any</i>		Bersani E., Bogoni B., <i>Morfologia urbana Mantova vol. 1</i> , Edizioni Unicopli, 2007.
<i>Websites: insert here the main references if any</i>		https://mantovasabbioneta-unesco.it
Building author /architect / artist	<i>Indicate the building author(s) / architect's name if it is known</i>	unknown
Construction period	<i>Look for documents about it</i>	17 th century
Archetypal definition	<p>terraced building _____</p> <p>courtyard building _____</p> <p>independent building _____</p> <p>flat _____</p> <p>other:.....</p>	Palazzetto
Original function		residential
Current function		residential
GEOGRAPHICAL/ADMINISTRATIVE LOCATION		Comments
Country	<i>Insert here</i>	Italy
Region	<i>Insert here</i>	Lombardy
Province	<i>Insert here</i>	Mantova
City	<i>Insert here</i>	Mantova
Address	<i>Insert here the address. Add, if possible, also a cadastral number</i>	Via Montanara e Curtatone
CLIMATIC CONDITIONS		Comments
Climate classification	<i>Check the climate classification according to the Köppen climate table</i>	Cfa - Humid Temperate climate
Heating Degree Days (HDD)	<i>Insert here considering HDD on 20°C, yearly: 2023</i>	2388
Cooling Degree Days (CDD)	<i>Insert here considering CDD on 26°C, yearly: 2023</i>	180
Building front façade orientation	<i>Indicate how the building front façade is positioned in relation to the sun paths in different seasons, as well as to prevailing wind patterns (e.g., main façade is oriented north-south, with a small courtyard directed to west catching winds in summer).</i>	East-West
Climatic file	<i>Indicate if a climatic file is present</i>	-
URBAN CONTEXT		Comments
Historical urban building framework		
<p><i>Insert here a summary of the urban framing of the building. Start from analysing the historical cartography for understanding the building complex evolution during time. Describe in max. 1000 characters</i></p> <p>The building dates back to the 17th century and we can find it in Ranieri's map (1831), overlooking the street then called Contrada Breda di Mezzo. It is located in what is the area of Mantua considered as suburb of the first and second circle (15th -19th centuries), characterized by dense and compact blocks that define a continuous building curtain on the street front. In this central area of Mantova many buildings are made up of gothic lots on which the building type of the Mantovan Palazzetto house insists.</p>		

Figure 1 - Example of page in the Building Identity Card section of the Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building. Extract about General Information, Climatic conditions, Urban context.

<p>Ranieri's map (1831). The circle with red dots indicates the case study position. Detail of the same Map, with the indication of the case study area.</p>											
Actual building urban context and location	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>city centre</td> <td>X</td> </tr> <tr> <td>outskirts</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>coastal area</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>wooded area / mountain</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>other:.....</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	city centre	X	outskirts		coastal area		wooded area / mountain		other:.....	
city centre	X										
outskirts											
coastal area											
wooded area / mountain											
other:.....											
Accessibility	<p>Indicate how the building is accessible (e.g. from a public street, from inside a private courtyard, etc.)</p> <p>from a public street</p>										
Overshadowing elements	<p>Indicate, if applicable, the location of overshadowing from trees or other buildings</p> <p>The building is overshadowed by other buildings on the other corner of the street in the afternoon</p>										
OWNERSHIP AND EXISTENCE OF PROTECTION CONSTRAINTS		Comments									
Legal status of the building	<p>Indicate if it is a public, private, mixed property, other</p> <p>Private property</p>										
Actors involved in the building management	<p>Indicate all the actors involved in the building management and use; describe also if different parts of the building have different owners/managers</p> <p>Single owner</p>										
Protection status of the building	<p>Insert the protection status description (e.g., National Register of Historic Places; Indirect protection under the Code n.42/2004, art. 45.)</p> <p>-</p>										
Landscape / context protection status	<p>Indicate if the building is part of a protected urban centre or an urban landscape (e.g., UNESCO World Heritage city perimeter). Describe and look for documents attesting that (e.g. landscape restrictions map; historical centre planning map)</p> <p>UNESCO protection area; PGT Areas with very high landscape sensitivity - Properties worthy of protection: grade 3 constraint; A2: Suburb of the first and second circle, art. D43, D44, D45</p>										
Building regulation constraints rules	<p>Description of the rules/duties implied by the building which is under a regulation protection (e.g., Listed Building Consent may be required if you're hoping to carry out any demolition, make any alterations to the appearance)</p> <p>Only interventions on the existing building stock within the limit of building renovation are allowed. Interventions on parts or portions of building units must in any case represent the consistency of the proposed action, in order to protect the unitary values of the building with a specific study extended to the entire unit; where necessary, this study must be extended to the surrounding context also for the purpose of verifying the landscape and the sensitivity of the intervention site [...]. For existing additions within the courtyards, building renovation interventions are allowed through partial or total demolition and reconstruction. (Piano delle regole del PGT, Art. D13 - Disposizioni generali per i nuclei di antica Formazione).</p>										
Attach any documents certifying the building protection constraints											

Figure 2 - Example of page in the Building Identity Card section of the Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building. Extract about Urban history, Use of the building, Ownership and constraints.

Brick load-bearing masonry is visible in the corridor, where some humidity problems requested to remove the plaster at the bottom of the wall, and in the attic level. Some reinforcements are present under the roof, probably due to some changes in the elevation of the last building level during time, creating a larger unique storage space and closing also the interior wind tower.

Roof		Notes/Drawings
Roof typologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe the roofing shape, system (e.g., trusses, domes, vaults) and materials (e.g., wood shingles, slate and metal, standing seam metal, etc.). - Also describe if there are several roof types (e.g., mansard roof, gable roof, terraced roof, etc.) - Provide a brief description of the layers of the roof components (e.g. from outside to inside: traditional terracotta roof tiles; wooden panels 2 cm; frame of pine wood beams and joists) - Annotate on plans with a code all different roof types (e.g. ROOF01, etc.) 	<p>Double-pitched roof with wooden planking, joists and wooden beams with a circular section. Since the dimension of the attic rooms is very large, there are support points for the roof structure with brick pillars. The ridge of the two pitches rests on the central spine wall of the building. External cladding in antique tiles.</p>
State of conservation	<p>Describe if roof typologies present visible defects/decay issues. Add if there has been any retrofit of this element already</p>	<p>The wooden structure of the roof is in a fair condition; it would be necessary to deepen its mechanical resistance.</p>
Decorative and valuable / authentic architectural elements	<p>Describe if the roof presents historic valuable architectural elements (e.g., tiles, skylights, chimneys, gutters and downspouts, etc.) and/or decorative systems worthy to be preserved (such as cresting and finials).</p>	<p>The roof has two openings like skylights now closed by windows. There is also an ancient turret for the ventilation of the building, which overlooks the roof tiles with a door.</p>

Double-pitched roof with wooden planking, joists and wooden beams with a circular section. Exterior view on the roof tiles.

Figure 3 - Example of page in the Building Identity Card section of the Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building. Extract about Roof description.

Floor		Notes/Drawings
Floor typologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe the main floor systems, including ground floor, inter-storey floors and ceilings - Provide a brief description of the layers of the floor components - Annotate on plans with a code all different floor types (e.g. FLOOR01, etc.) 	The floor is composed by a wooden floorboard resting on a framework of joists and main beams. The cladding is in square terracotta tiles.
State of conservation	Describe if different floor typologies present decay (e.g., deformation, partial substitution, etc.). Add if there has been any retrofit of this element already	<p>All floors appear in good state of conservation.</p> <p>In some cases where the floor is exposed, the addition of more recent joists (on the second floor) has been found.</p> <p>It could be necessary to verify the stability at the point of interlocking in the walls.</p>
Valuable elements - ceiling level	<p>Describe if there are valuable elements at the ceiling level (e.g., exposed decorated beams, vaults, frescoes, etc.).</p> <p>Describe if there are valuable historical elements in the ceiling section (e.g. as technical ducts, etc.).</p>	The false ceiling is made of reed and plaster mortar and is characterized by oval decorative stuccoes placed in the centre of the room, with a pattern that encased the wooden beams. In some rooms this false ceiling has been removed.
Valuable / authentic elements - other floors	<p>Describe the presence of valuable elements on the top of the floor (e.g. the presence of ventilation grilles; floor cladding – in 'tiles', 'floorboards', etc.).</p> <p>Describe if there are valuable historical elements in the floor section (e.g. as technical ducts, etc.).</p>	In the area of the corridor on the ground floor, some wall decorations, dating back to the late 19th century, have also been removed from the floor ceiling.

Exposed wooden floor, where you can see how reinforcement joists have been added in more recent times. Ceiling in reed, under a layer of gypsum mortar. Decorations found in the corridor leading to the courtyard, from the late 19th century.

Figure 4 - Example of page in the Building Identity Card section of the Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building. Extract about Floors description.

2.2. Building Value assessment

According to EN 16883:2017, an essential step in the building knowledge process involves identifying the heritage significance of building materials, construction techniques, and components, as well as architectural adornments, fixtures, fittings, and technologies. A detailed analysis of these character-defining elements helps to assess their vulnerability to change and their potential to reveal or enhance heritage values. This process supports also the understanding of conservation aspirations from owners and stakeholders, as well as the priorities or constraints outlined by heritage authorities.

In line with the standard's guidance, the second section of the survey sheet introduces a structured system to assist compilers in identifying the full spectrum of values associated with a historic building. It is intended as a comprehensive guide to safeguard a multidimensional understanding of significance, ensuring thorough documentation and cross-referencing with historical records and expert consultations, where necessary.

The categories of heritage values indicated in literature (Avrami et al., 2020; Elwazani, 2021; Forsyth, 2007; Orbasli, 2008; Smith, 2006) focused on the heritage significance valuing and considered in this assessment include (Figures 5-6):

- **Historical values** - Historical values are essential to the very notion of heritage. This type of value consists of different concepts, and it highlights the capacity of a site to convey, embody, or stimulate a relation or reaction to the past. Historical value can include the age of construction and built material, the use of the building by historically significant people, institutions, events or context. The historical value may depend on the building uniqueness, rarity, and its potential to be a source of archival/documentary value. In literature we can find two important subtypes of historical value: educational/academic value and historical artistic value. The first lies in the potential to gain knowledge about the past through archaeology, construction history or an interpretation of historical records, that may be also linked to the presence of notable figures. The second value is based on the building being an example of a certain art movement (e.g., Renaissance, Industrial Revolution, etc.);
- **Cultural and symbolic values** - There is no heritage without cultural value. This category overlaps with the historical one and it refers to those shared meanings associated with heritage that are not related to the chronological aspects and meanings of a site. The cultural value refers to the importance or value placed on certain aspects of culture by individuals or communities. These aspects could include traditions, customs, symbols, beliefs, art forms, or historical sites that hold special meaning;
- **Social values** - It denotes the significance of places that bring a sense of identity, belonging, and association through people, places, and shared social experiences. It is the underlying motivation for common practices that are present in intangible forms such as memory and oral history, which define the genealogy of a community. These values enable and facilitate social connections, networks, and other relations in a broad sense, not necessarily related to the historical values of the building. Social values can include also the use of a site for socializing, on the ground of the symbolic value associated to the building (e.g. a church);

- **Aesthetic values** - Aesthetics refers to the visual values of heritage. It is intended to be considered in a broader context than just beauty, but also of cultural identity, historical memory and emotional connection. Aesthetic value is what makes something beautiful, harmonious, interesting or exciting from a visual or artistic point of view. So, it will address the presence of key design features (materials, decorations, furniture), as well as the presence of artistic significance for a special craftsmanship quality.
In the aesthetic value, also the visual relationship with the surroundings is included. The relationship between a construction and the surrounding landscape and environment is important to be preserved for maintaining the cultural urban and social equilibrium. Values attributed to a landscape correspond to an attachment or emotional bond that people develop with places. There are strong cultural ties to landscapes and feelings for the visual beauty of mountains, lakes, coasts, forests, etc., which are a common bond among people or social groups of a given region. Differently, environmental value is linked to non-human phenomena that humans interact with, embracing our responsibility to care for and protect the environment for future generations. The definition of the visual relationship with the surroundings, considering this both as landscape and as environment, can answer the questions "in what context is the heritage building inserted? How the building is in relation with the existing elements (e.g. streets, other buildings, natural/artificial landscape, etc.)? Is it an environment of exceptional value?";
- **Scientific values** - It is attributed to consider the preservation and promotion of certain qualities or features which have scientific significance. It is linked, for instance, to special technical solutions implemented in the building;
- **Architectural values** -This refers to complex qualities of heritage, referring mainly to construction characterizing elements in relation to traditions or innovation in a certain period and place. Architecture is considered as very subjective value type, requiring high competences in heritage to be identified.

This process of identifying values is thought to be applicable both to buildings that are *listed* or subject to local binding restrictions, as well as those that are not. A listed building is typically recognized by local or national conservation authorities for its cultural, historical, or architectural significance. However, the existence of legal protection does not necessarily encompass all the values that could emerge from a broader heritage assessment. Similarly, a building that is not formally listed may still possess qualities that justify its preservation.

- **In the case of listed buildings or those with restrictions**, this section of the sheet should be completed by consulting the opinion of the local conservation authority and/or related documentation, identifying the elements that justified the imposition of the legal constraint. It is also necessary to describe how these constraints may influence renovation planning—for example, if only maintenance is allowed, or if alterations to façades or interiors are prohibited; or if a landscape restriction limits the addition of visible elements such as rooftop solar panels.

Additionally, the following sheet can be used to identify whether there are further values beyond those covered by the legal designation.

- **In the case of non-listed buildings**, the sheet should still be completed to recognize any existing values. When possible, consult the local conservation authority's opinion and documents to identify elements that could justify future legal protection. This analysis can be supported by a detailed understanding of the building's transformation over time up to the present day.

Building Values Assessment

This section of the sheet should be used as a comprehensive guide to assess the full spectrum of values that a historic building may possess, safeguarding a comprehensive understanding of its significance across multiple dimensions. Ensure thorough documentation and cross-reference with historical records and expert consultations where necessary.

IF THE BUILDING IS LISTED / PRESENT LOCAL BINDING RESTRICTIONS	IF THE BUILDING IS NOT LISTED / DO NOT PRESENT BINDING RESTRICTIONS
A listed building usually is recognised by the local/national conservation authority for its values. However, it is not a given that the assignment of the constraint includes all the parameters falling within a heritage value assessment.	If a building is not formally listed, this doesn't mean that it hasn't values that make it worthy to be preserved.
Consult your local conservation authority's opinion and/or documents in describing what are the elements that led to the recognition of a legal constraint.	Compile the following sheet to recognise the presence of values. For a better support, consult your local conservation authority's opinion and/or documents in describing what are the elements that led to the recognition of a legal constraint.
Describe how the building constraints may affect the planning of renovation interventions (e.g., in the building it is only possible to proceed with maintenance activities and it is forbidden to modify the facades as well as the interiors; the landscape restriction which the building is subject poses a limit in adding elements on the facades and visible from the street as solar panels on the roof; ..)	This analysis can be addressed through a detailed knowledge of the building transformation process to the present.
Compile the following sheet to recognise the additional presence of values in comparison with the legal constraint.	

VALUES ASSESSMENT

Historical values		Comments
Historical significance	<p>Compile if, for example the building/a portion of that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It's considered an important architecture for key events (e.g., battles, treaties, etc.); - It's considered important for the presence of notable figures (e.g., past owners, residents, architects, etc.); - It has/had a role in local/national history; - It belongs to a period of significance (e.g., Renaissance, Industrial Revolution, etc.); - It has documentary evidence through records (e.g., archives, maps, photographs), oral histories and/or publications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It belongs to the 17th century • It has documentary evidence through historic maps (i.e. Ranieri's map)
Cultural values		Comments
Cultural significance	<p>Compile if, for example, the building/a portion of that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It has a role in local/national cultural identity (e.g., considering it as part of a landscape, as part of a historic centre, as a landmark); - It has a symbolic meaning (e.g., for its 	It is part of the Mantova historic centre.

Figure 5 - Example of page in the Building Values Assessment section of the Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building. Extract about Values identification.

D5.2 Cultural heritage analysis and value assessment

	<p><i>religious importance, for the national pride, for cultural associations, etc);</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>It is considered connected to the local intangible heritage (e.g., it is a place where local festivals, rituals took place, etc.)</i> 		
Social values			Comments
Community importance	<p><i>Compile if, for example, the building/a portion of that:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>It has local significance as meeting place</i> 	-	
Social function	<p><i>Compile if, for example, the building/a portion of that:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>It hosted historical social functions (e.g., courthouse, town hall, etc.)</i> - <i>It hosts current social uses (e.g., a community centre, a museum, etc.)</i> 	-	
Social memory	<p><i>Compile if, for example, the building/a portion of that:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>It is linked to collective memory (e.g., local stories, commemorations)</i> - <i>It had a role in historical social movements (e.g., protests, gatherings)</i> 	-	
Community engagement	<p><i>Compile if, for example, the building/a portion of that:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>It is important for the community use (e.g., events, gatherings, etc.)</i> - <i>It has an educational value (e.g., learning opportunities, for outreach programs)</i> 	-	
Aesthetic values			Comments
Key design features	<p><i>Compile if, for example, the building/a portion of that:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>It has at the exterior ornaments (e.g., stucco decorations, mouldings, decorated window string courses, frames)</i> - <i>It has exterior unique, precious, ancient materials (e.g., antique facade finishes, fine materials, etc.);</i> - <i>It has at the interior special decorations (e.g., frescoes, tapestries, etc.)</i> - <i>It has historic furniture (fixed or movable)</i> 	<p><i>On the outside it does not have any valuable elements. Inside, however, there are numerous relevant elements: frescoes of different dates, reed ceilings with stuccoes from the late '800. Nothing remains inside of the antique furniture.</i></p>	
Visual relationships	<p><i>Compile if, for example, the building/a portion of that:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>It demonstrates the presence of visual relationships with the surroundings (e.g., through a landscape integration, through</i> 	<p><i>The building is part of the building curtain of the seventeenth-century historic centre of Mantua.</i></p>	

Figure 6 - Example of page in the Building Values Assessment section of the Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building. Extract about Values identification.

Once heritage values have been identified, the assessment of the state of the building in terms of authenticity follows as the next step. The term authenticity/integrity refers to the preservation of the building’s significant characteristics over time summarizing which parts of the building have been altered over time, rather than to its perfect conservation. It indicates that the historical and cultural values of the site have not been altered by external or inappropriate interventions.

Indeed, the assessment should describe whether the building—or specific parts of it—has undergone comprehensive or localized restorations or modifications (e.g., extensions, additions, replacements). It should also evaluate whether these changes are compatible with the historic structure. Additionally, the current state of conservation of the modified elements should be noted, including possible causes of decay. This evaluation helps to understand how the building's evolution has aimed to preserve certain values and to better guide future retrofit interventions toward compatible solutions.

<p>Authenticity</p>	<p>Describe the state of the building in term of authenticity, summarizing which parts have been changed in the building. So:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe if the building/ part of it has been subject of global or punctual restorations / interventions (e.g., extension/additions, substitutions, etc.) - Describe if present modifications and alterations are compatible respect to the historic construction <p>For example: The rooms on the ground floor are coeval with the building period of construction and only the windows were replaced in the nineteenth century. The staircase was instead inserted in 1945. On the first and second levels, fan coils have been inserted in the rooms impacting on the building integrity. Rooms were divided for residential use with partitions in the 80s of the XX century, making complex the spaces reading. The windows are all new in PVC. The vaulted ceilings have been removed, leaving exposed the decorated floor wooden beams of the seventeenth century. Interior plasters hide portions of ancient frescoes that should be investigated and could be put on display. The floors are in marble grit from the 50s. On the outside, the façade has recently been redone with a lime-based plaster, which is compatible with the underlying masonry.</p>	<p>The rooms on the ground floor are coeval with the building period of construction and only the windows were replaced in the nineteenth century. The staircase was instead inserted in 1945. Rooms were divided for residential use with partitions in the 80s of the 900s, making more complex the spaces reading. The windows were replaced during time with others in wood, while old shutters were kept. The false ceilings have been removed in some rooms, leaving exposed the wooden floor of the seventeenth century. Interior plasters hide portions of ancient wall paintings that should be investigated and could be put on display. The floors are in ancient terracotta tiles, except for the second floor where they are new ones. On the outside, the façade has recently been redone with a lime-based plaster, which is compatible with the underlying masonry.</p>	
<p>State of conservation of the modified parts</p>	<p>Describe the state of conservation of modified parts, possibly also inserting the cause of the decay.</p> <p>For example: Fan coils do not work well and create internal discomfort. The new PVC windows at first and second levels are all ruined; in some of them the glass is missing due to lack of maintenance. The new façade is perfectly maintained.</p>	<p>The new wooden windows are in good conditions. On the other hand, the closing window of the wind tower is in very poor condition. The new finishing of the main façade is perfectly maintained.</p>	

Figure 7 - Example of page in the Authenticity section of the Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building.

2.3. Summary Sheet testing process

To demonstrate the validity of the developed survey sheet, HeriTACE heritage expert partners were asked to complete the Summary sheet for the selected case studies in each partner country.

The developed built heritage characteristics analysis methodology was applied to case-study buildings for each of the HeriTACE archetypes. The survey involved several expert practitioners from each partner country (Belgium, Norway, Estonia, Italy), leading to a calibration of the tool in relation to the very different heritage protection frameworks and traditional building practices across these countries. In each country a selection /the whole group of case studies was used for the testing phase of the summary sheet.

Conservation experts performed also the cultural heritage analysis of building values for each case study, following those considered as 'actual conservation theories' in the present time, which were previously discussed and agreed in the specialized group of heritage researchers within the HeriTACE project.

The testing process through case studies made it possible to gather feedback on the tool. The successful outcome of the testing phase led to the final and jointly developed version of the sheet, which is placed within the ZENODO platform as indicated in the Annex 1.

The results of the individual applications to the case studies in different countries are presented in the following sections in summary (Sections 2-5). For privacy reasons, the completed forms have been collected and placed within the ZENODO platform, as indicated in the Annex 1 as well.

2.3.1. Connection of analysed case studies to Heritage Value scenarios

Cultural heritage building analysis and value assessment activities were useful for better identifying the conservation status of each case study, as well as supporting the understanding of which interventions may be considered allowable for the various construction elements while preserving their peculiarities and values.

Indeed, the outcome of heritage values assessment made by the HeriTACE project heritage experts may be considered as case-specific, and thus different values can be observed within each townhouse archetype example; moreover, local differences in the conservation discourse led also to subtle differences in the conservation and renovation advice.

However, the assessment of the case studies also made it possible to identify the main specificities of each case and each archetype – namely, the heritage value scenario at the building level – and to understand which intervention strategies, at the component level, could generally be considered acceptable within each scenario, particularly in the context of energy efficiency improvements aligned with conservation objectives. These two aspects are crucial for achieving the broader goal of the HeriTACE project: developing replicable renovation strategies for the defined archetypes.

Therefore, the heritage assessment of real case studies enabled a structured dialogue among heritage experts on two key fronts: on the one hand, the establishment of agreed 'levels of impact' for retrofit interventions on historic buildings, thus allowing a better understanding of which transformations can be considered compatible with the

preservation of cultural significance; on the other, the definition of generalised heritage value scenarios for building archetypes.

So, the first step in the discussion among heritage experts was to agree on common categories (for all countries involved) that express which interventions are allowed when considering a historic building. These categories apply at component level (see Figure 8). More additional information is reported in the following subparagraph.

As a second generalisation step, in all participating countries, the local experts developed baseline heritage value scenarios (HV) at building level, in which each time the categories of allowable measures are specified for the building components (focussing on the components that could be impacted by energy-related renovation of the building).

The recognition that different levels of constraints can lead to significantly different intervention choices – even among buildings recognised with the same archetype – prompted the need to define “typical” value scenarios. These were based on experts’ knowledge of the cultural significance of analysed archetypes and on the detailed analysis of the HeriTACE case studies. Hence, the resulting heritage value scenarios represent recurring situations and serve as a foundation for the development of both baseline and HeriTACE renovation solutions that respect the heritage value. Defined HV range from the highest level, applied to archetype examples considered of monumental relevance, to buildings without any value, applied to archetype cases located in historic contexts but lacking any identifiable heritage value. A more detailed overview of the HV scenarios is documented per country in D5.4.

For most of the cases within the archetypes under study, a ‘close-by’ heritage value scenario could be identified. The HeriTACE case studies focus on intermediate heritage value scenarios, which are the most representative and replicable for the townhouse archetypes. While historic buildings of the highest value are typically those identified as monumental or listed – where material and constructive authenticity has been preserved over time and only maintenance and restoration operations are permitted – historic townhouses have usually undergone partial or complete modifications to their envelope and interiors. Nevertheless, they still retain elements of authenticity and heritage value.

The attribution of HV scenarios at building level to the individual case studies is documented per country in the consecutive Sections.

2.3.2. Categories of allowable measures at building component level considering cultural heritage value

The defined categories of allowable measures at building component level considering cultural heritage value cover the spectrum from very strict conservation (“zero”-category) to situations where no value restrictions apply (category 4).

In the following, examples for each of the five categories are collected. Additional examples are provided in the Annex 2.

Figure 8 - Categories of allowable measures at building component level considering cultural heritage value.

Category 0: Only conservation measures allowed

In this category only conservation and necessary maintenance activities are possible. As quoted in the UNESCO glossary, conservation related to buildings involves a range of actions to maintain, protect, and manage change to heritage assets or listed buildings. This means that in this category, measures applicable from maintenance to restoration of the existing elements are considered. The latter would be recommended also if it is considered necessary to remove something not coherent with the construction (e.g. recent additions or inadequate adaptations to the building), in order to re-establish a more historically correct situation.

Energy-related interventions are not allowed here, as they will have impact on the authentic material, form, or finishes. Any measure, maintenance- and restoration wise, in this category might also induce damage risks to the building and should thus be thoroughly elaborated before implementation.

Category 1: Low impact measures allowed

This category allows low impact solutions, considered to be reversible in the future and/or removable without affecting the authentic materials, form, and finishes in a permanent way, and/or causing decay. Energy-related solutions can be included, considering the criteria of minimum intervention, compatibility, and reversibility.

This category may include, for example, cladding of the internal walls with dry and removable systems (e.g. curtains, structures in self-supporting panels as false walls) that do not affect the existing wall either during installation or at the end of its life. For the openings (windows and doors), it also includes installing joints to reduce air leaks, inserting solar films and installing any shading systems such as removable internal blinds. For roofing, it can include the installation of insulation in the attic floor, which is easily maintained and removable.

Figure 9 - Example of low impact measures allowed at building component level considering cultural heritage value.

Category 2: Medium impact measure allowed

This category allows to provide energy-related improvements to original components, by making additions and/or small and compatible substitutions. The aim is to preserve the existing historic elements with their material value as much as possible, as well as maintaining the overall aesthetic appearance of the building components. Hence, the allowed solutions avoid for example huge holes, drillings, demolitions, and dismissions of elements. This category may also apply in situations where previously made erroneous changes (e.g. inappropriate regarding heritage value or technically damaging) require reversion to a situation that is close to the original (e.g. same material, and similar design), but with an improved energy performance as compared to the original situation.

This category may include, for example, substituting the existing glass pane with one more performant, adjusting the thickness to host it in the window frame with a handmade work, or adding an interior secondary window in an interior without valuable finishes, while preserving the original window on the exterior. In the retrofit of wall components, this can include the replacement of the ruined old plaster with a compatible nanotechnological material (e.g. natural-based, which guarantees a certain breathability of the masonry, as well as a certain texture and colour) and also the addition of interior insulation, if no decorations are present and if the interior space guarantee a certain liveability of interiors. For roofing, this can include the addition of interior insulation at roof level, if no decorations are present.

* If there are no decorations/ valuable surfaces

Figure 10 - Example of medium impact measures allowed at building component level considering cultural heritage value.

Category 3: High impact measures allowed

In this category, it is possible to remove existing elements and replace them with new ones. No historicising replacement is envisaged, but the new elements must harmonise with the surrounding materials and context. In this case, the existing elements have low heritage value, date from a later construction phase that does not harmonise with the surrounding materials and context, or are too damaged to enable a repair. This is only possible if the heritage protection status of the building does not require restoration to the original model or the preservation of the original materials. The shape and proportions of the building might not be altered, if restrictions at neighbourhood level might apply.

This category may include, for example, adding additional insulation to the internal and external walls according to the current practices. Change of façade finishing concept is possible, replacing old windows and doors with modern energy-efficient ones (the appearance of windows can be altered), changing roof covering with different one, compared to old material, etc.

In this category we can also consider replacing damaged parts with copy of original ones (wooden boarding); altering the proportions is avoided wherever possible; windows are either restored or installed new ones similar to original, but with added energy-efficient glazing; in some cases new roof-windows or dormers can be added to convert attic to living space.

- In this category we can also consider replacing damaged parts with copy of original ones

Figure 11 - Example of high impact measures allowed at building component level considering cultural heritage value.

Category 4: Any measures allowed

In this category, no restrictions are imposed from a heritage perspective. Although substitutions of materials, shapes or finishes should not be done according to original model or should not refer to an original version, the structure of the building cannot be altered (no new window openings, no new floor structure, ...).

This category would also apply to new buildings, inserted in historic neighbourhoods.

3. Belgium: application in case studies

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3.1. Case studies overview

The testing of the summary sheet has been focused on 11 case studies in Ghent, as listed in the following.

Table 1: Summary of the testing phase method in the Belgian case studies.

Case studies	Archetype	Survey method	Survey team
MEERS 	Middle-class townhouse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Archival research • Collection of the original architectural drawings • Technical installations data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service of Urban Archaeology and Heritage, City of Ghent (GENT): (building identity card and value assessment) • UGent (building identity card and technical installations data collection)
BREDERODE 	Middle-class townhouse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Technical installations data collection 	
CITADEL 	Middle-class townhouse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Archival research • Collection of the original architectural drawings • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	

Case studies	Archetype	Survey method	Survey team
<p>EYCK</p>	<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite Analysis • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service of Urban Archaeology and Heritage, City of Ghent (GENT): (building identity card and value assessment) • UGent (building identity card and technical installations data collection)
<p>MUINK</p>	<p>private mansion</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Archival research • Collection of the original architectural drawings • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	
<p>HERT</p>	<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Archival research • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	
<p>MARTENS1</p>	<p>Modest House</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	

Case studies	Archetype	Survey method	Survey team
<p>MARTENS2</p>	<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service of Urban Archaeology and Heritage, City of Ghent (GENT): (building identity card and value assessment) • UGent (building identity card and technical installations data collection)
<p>KUIPER</p>	<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	
<p>KONING</p>	<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	
<p>KEIZER</p>	<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Archival research • Consultation of the original architectural drawings • Consultation of the architectural heritage inventory • Technical installations data collection 	

3.2. Main findings of application results

After compiling the Summary Sheet for each case study, all collected data has been summarized into two tables: one indicating all information related to the Building Identity Cards of the Belgian case studies (Table 2) and another for collecting information on their Building Value Assessment and identification of Authenticity (Table 3). This process of synthesizing descriptive data has made it possible to clarify possible similarities between different cases, albeit strictly within the same country/city and therefore in the same climatic and geographical context.

What emerged from the Belgian cases is mainly that:

MEERS

- Early 20th-century terraced house, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a gable roof and a street facade with two bays. There are several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, doors, plaster consoles, staircase, etc.) and on the street façade. The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century outskirts of the city. The elegant street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has historical and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. Except for some interventions in the interior, the building has retained its original structure, layout, decorative exterior elements and most of its interior elements (ground and first floor). In the street façade the addition of glazing beads on some windows and the application of a filler on the plaster have slightly impacted the building's authenticity, but these alterations are reversible. The other modifications have caused a limited impact on the heritage value and authenticity of the property. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value of the street façade: the roof, the rear façade (already equipped with exterior wall insulation), and the previously replaced windows of the rear façade, which were installed in a disruptive manner. Although removal of the filler on the street façade is desirable, the underlying original plaster and decoration must be preserved, therefore exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. When replacing the windows and the door of the street façade, this can be done with energy-efficient joinery, but with a similar material, layout, and detailing as the original joinery so the aesthetic appearance is preserved.

BREDERODE

- End 19th-century terraced house, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value, but it's not included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a gable roof and a street facade with two bays. There are some valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks, staircase, doors, etc.) and on the street façade. The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century

outskirts of the city. The elegant street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical and architectural value

- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_III.2. This building has already been the subject of interventions, but it retained its original structure and layout. In the interior, many original features have been preserved. The street façade has been renovated with respect for the original material and details, but all the exterior doors and windows have been replaced with contemporary joinery with a loss of heritage value. Only the window on the ground floor was designed to the original model. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value or of elements that have no heritage status: the roof, the rear façade and the previously replaced windows. The original plaster on the street façade must be preserved, therefore exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. When replacing the windows and the door of the street façade, this can be done with modern energy-efficient joinery.

CITADEL

- Mid-19th-century terraced house, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are four floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a gable roof and a street facade with three bays. There are several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks, staircase, doors, etc.) and on the street façade. The finishing of the rear façade (annex and main volume) is authentic and valuable. The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century outskirts of the city. The elegant street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical, aesthetic and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_I. This building has already been the subject of some interventions. The building structure of the main volume, internal layout and circulation have been preserved completely. One room is a later addition and has no heritage value. The rear building is authentic and has heritage value concerning the volume, interior staircase, exterior and window in the staircase. The front façade has remained its original architecture, including the windows except for the glass. The back façade has its original layout and a valuable rendering but in this façade the windows have no heritage value. In the interior, many original features have been preserved, especially on the ground floor. The upper floors are more sober and have originally fewer interior features.

According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value: the roof and the previously replaced windows of the rear façade. The original plaster on the street and on the rear façade must be preserved, therefore exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. Preferably, the original windows and door of the street façade and the staircase window of the annex are to be preserved, but thermal

improvements such as sealing strips or the addition of a window on the interior side of the staircase window are possible.

EYCK

- Late 19th-century terraced house, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a mansard roof and a street facade with three bays and a balcony. The main building is authentic and has a street façade and interior with a distinct heritage value (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks, staircase, doors, etc.). The volume of the kitchen is authentic, but the interior has been changed in 1996. The building is a typical example of a 19th-century townhouse with an elegant street façade. The building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. This building has kept most of its original architecture. In the street façade all the windows were replaced with wooden frames according to the original model and profiling but were fitted with double glazing. The original fittings were reused. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value: the roof (except for the mansard part including the dormers), the rear façade and the previously replaced windows of the rear façade. The street façade must be preserved; therefor exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. Thermal improvements of the windows of the street façade are possible but as these windows are already renewed with respect for the layout and details of the original joinery, they can probably be retained and modified by the addition of sealing strips or more efficient double glazing.

MUINK

- Terraced house dating from the mid-19th-century, corresponding to the private mansion archetype. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a gable roof and a street facade with four bays, with the left one containing the gate of the driveway. The first floor has a balcony and a bay window. There are several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks, staircase, doors, etc.) and on the street façade. The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century outskirts of the city. The prominent street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical, aesthetic and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. This building has already been the subject of some interventions, but it retained its original structure and layout completely, except for the roof terrace on

the streetside. In the interior, the original features have been preserved, such as fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks; interior doors, etc. The street façade has been renovated in 2007 with respect for the original concept whilst preserving many of the authentic features. Nevertheless, in the street façade all the windows have been replaced with contemporary wooden joinery with a loss of heritage value. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value: the roof, the rear façade and the previously replaced windows. The original plaster on the street façade must be preserved, therefore exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. When replacing the windows of the street façade, this could be done with energy-efficient wooden joinery, but with a layout, and detailing according to the original 19th-century model. So, this becomes a reverse tot a situation that is close to the original but with an improved energy performance.

HERT

- Early 20th-century terraced house, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a gable roof and a street facade with two bays and a balcony. There are several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, doors, plaster consoles, staircase, etc.) and on the street façade. The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century outskirts of the city. The elegant street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_I. This building has retained its original structure and layout completely. In the interior the original features have been preserved, such as fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks; interior doors, etc. Some changes were done to the former service rooms in the annex, but these rooms were of secondary importance. The street façade itself has been renovated and maintained with great attention to detail. It is basically impeccable. Only the windows on the second floor have been removed with a loss of heritage value. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value: the roof, the rear façade and the previously replaced windows of the rear façade. The street façade must be preserved; therefore exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. Thermal improvements of the original windows of the street façade could be the addition of sealing strips or more efficient double glazing. When replacing the two windows of the street façade that had been changed before, this should be done with wooden windows according to the original model, but a thermal improvement and double glazing is possible. So, this becomes a reverse tot a situation that is close to the original but with an improved energy performance.

MARTENS1

- Early 20th-century terraced house, corresponding to the modest house archetype. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a mansard roof and a street façade with two bays and a balcony on the first floor. There are some valuable elements in the interior. The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century outskirts of the city. The elegant street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. This building has already been the subject of interventions: most of the windows (both street and rear façade) were replaced with wooden frames and double glazing; some false ceilings had been added in the interior and some walls and their finishes were customized. Only in the street façade on the ground floor the original door and window were preserved. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value: the roof, the rear façade and the previously replaced windows of the rear façade. The street façade with its glazed bricks must be preserved; therefore exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. Thermal improvements of the original window of the ground floor in the street façade could be the addition of sealing strips or replacing the glass by double glazing. When replacing the windows of the street façade that had been changed before, this should be done with wooden windows according to the original model, but a thermal improvement and double glazing is possible. So, this becomes a reversible situation that is close to the original but with an improved energy performance.

MARTENS2

- Early 20th-century terraced house, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a mansard roof and a street facade with two bays and a bay window. There are several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, doors, plaster consoles, staircase, etc.) and on the street façade. The building is a typical example of an early 20th-century townhouse. The elegant street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_I. This building has retained its original structure and layout. In the interior the original features have been preserved, such as fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks; interior doors, etc. Some changes were done at the annex, but this façade and interior were of secondary importance. The street façade itself has been restored and maintained with great attention to detail. It is basically impeccable. The windows were renewed according to the original model but were provided with thin double-glazing and sealing strips. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell

that do not impact the heritage value: the roof (except for the mansard part with the dormers at the street side), the rear façade and the previously replaced windows of the rear façade. The street façade must be preserved; therefore exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. As the windows of the street façade are already renewed according to the original model but with the addition of thin double glazing and sealing strips, it is logical and sustainable to maintain them.

KUIPER

- Late 19th-century terraced house, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a mansard roof and a street facade with three bays and a bay window. There are some valuable elements in the interior (two fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, doors, staircase, etc.) and on the street façade. The building is a typical example of a late 19th-century townhouse. The prominent street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_III.3. The complete building still has its authentic structure and layout, but the interior and the rear façade have been recently renewed in which a lot of finishings and decorations disappeared. The street façade remained its valuable architecture and details except for the windows. All the windows of the street and rear façade were replaced by plastic windows. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value: the roof (except for the mansard part with the dormer at the street side), the rear façade and the previously replaced windows. The original architecture of the street façade must be preserved; therefore exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. When replacing the windows of the street façade, this should be done with wooden windows according to the original 19th-century model, but a thermal improvement and double glazing is possible. So, this becomes a reverse to a situation that is close to the original but with an improved energy performance.

KONING

- Presumably 17th-century terraced house, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a gable roof and a 19th century street façade with three bays. There are several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, doors, plaster consoles, staircase, etc.) and on the street façade. The building has a rich history with clearly recognizable 18th-century and 19th-century construction phases. The street façade is a typical example of a 19th-century plastered façade. This façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements illustrate the historical and architectural value of the building.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_I. This building has already been the subject of a restoration. Except for a few

elements and finishes in the interior, the house has retained its 17th, 18th or 19th century structure, layout, and decorative exterior and interior elements. The windows of the street façade and these of the rear façade ground floor were renewed according to the original model but were provided with thin double-glazing and sealing strips. The other windows of the rear façade were changed by modern wooden windows with a similar design but with more performant double glazing. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value: the roof, the rear façade and the previously replaced windows of the rear façade. The street façade must be preserved; therefor exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. As the windows of the street façade are already renewed according to the original model but we the addition of thin double glazing and sealing strips, it is logical and sustainable to maintain them.

KEIZER

- Terraced house dating from the mid-19th-century, corresponding to the middle-class townhouse. The house is located in the zone with cultural and/or aesthetic value and has been included on the architectural heritage inventory. There are three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic. The building has a gable roof and a street facade with three bays and a bay window. There are several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks, staircase, doors, etc.) and on the street façade. The building is a typical example of a 19th-century townhouse. The elegant street façade, the building volume, the layout and the interior elements are characteristic for this type of residence from this construction period. The building has an historical and architectural value.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. The building has retained its original structure and layout. In the interior, the original features have been preserved, such as fireplaces with mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks; interior doors, etc. The original architecture of the street façade was preserved except for the renewal of some windows by non-authentic windows. The windows of the ground floor and the bay windows are still authentic, except for the glass. The back façade has its original layout, but the change of rendering has done damage to the authenticity. In the interior, many original features have been preserved, especially on the ground floor. The upper floors are more sober and had originally fewer interior features. Elements have been removed, especially on the third floor. According to the heritage status it is conceivable, to improve the thermal characteristics of the exterior shell that do not impact the heritage value: the roof, the rear façade and the previously replaced windows. The original plaster on the street façade must be preserved, therefor exterior insulation is not an option on this façade. Preferably, the remaining original windows and door of the street façade are to be preserved, but thermal improvements such as sealing strips or double glazing with reduced thickness are possible.

Table 2: Summary of the Building Identity Card section in the Belgian case studies.

Name	ARCHETYPE	CONSTRUCTION PERIOD	OWNER	ACTUAL USE	LEGAL CONSTRAINTS	MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES						STATE OF CONSERVATION
						Structure	Wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	Interiors elements	
MEERS	Middle-class townhouse	Building permit 2 May 1902	private	Single family house	CHE-area (Zone regional plan with cultural and/or aesthetic value) according to Regional Plan (Royal Decree 28/12/1972)	mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints and plaster on both sides (exterior: original plaster street façade / new plaster + insulation rear façade)	Several typologies of original floors (trough vaults / wooden beam structure) +moulded plaster ceilings + wooden planks or new tiles	Original gable roof with wooden purlins + glass roof (annex)	Several typologies of windows, including some original wooden windows in the street façade and 1 in the rear façade.	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, doors, plaster consoles, staircase, etc.) and on street façade.	The building is generally in good condition. There is limited moisture damage on the inside of the gable roof.
BREDERODE	Middle-class townhouse	Building permit 1882				mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick and concrete vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints + original plaster exterior street façade + plaster in the interior	Several typologies of floors (trough vaults / iron and concrete floor / wooden beam structure) with (partly) moulded ceilings / mostly original floors (wooden planks and tiles) and partly new floors	Original gable roof with wooden purlins + flat roof (annex).	new wooden windows of which 1 window based on a historical reference (ground floor street façade)+new steel front door	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, doors, plaster consoles, staircase etc.) and on street façade.	No substantial structural problems or pathologies detected. The building is generally in good condition.
CITADEL	Middle-class townhouse	Building permit 1882			CHE-area (Zone regional plan with cultural and/or aesthetic value) according to Regional Plan (Royal Decree 28/12/1972)+	mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints and plaster on both sides (exterior: original lime plaster street façade / partly simili-pierre, partly roughcast plaster on the rear façade and annex)	Several typologies of floors (trough vaults / wooden beam structure) with moulded ceilings / partly original, partly new tiles and presumably original wooden planks finished with vinyl flooring	Original gable roof with wooden purlins + flat roof (annex) +slanted roof on wooden joists (annex)	street façade: original wooden windows and door / rear façade: plastic windows / annex: partly original wooden windows, partly plastic windows	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, doors, staircase etc.), the entire street façade and the plasters of the rear façade.	The building is generally in good condition. There are damage cracks and pollution visible on the plaster of the back façade. The trough vaults show signs of corrosion.
EYCK	Middle-class townhouse	1875-1900			inventory heritage buildings (Immovable Heritage Decree 12/07/2013 - Section 4)	mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints and natural stone on the exterior of the street façade / plaster in the interior / rear façade simili-pierre / annex renewed cement-based plaster	Several typologies of original floors (trough vaults / wooden beam structure) +moulded plaster ceilings + partly original, partly new finishing (wooden planks/ tiles)	original tent roof with mansard part on the street side with wooden purlins + glazed roof (veranda) + semi tent roof (annex)	street facade: wooden windows renewed similar to the original ones / annex+rear façade+veranda: new wooden windows	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, moulded plaster ceilings, plaster consoles, panelling, doors, staircase etc.) and on street façade.	Good state of conservation. Only at the 2nd floor (room 3.4.) some presence of water infiltration. Problem seems to be solved.
MUINK	Private mansion	Building permit 1860 + alteration 1909			CHE-area (Zone regional plan with cultural and/or aesthetic value) according to	mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints and plaster on both sides (exterior: original plaster street façade / new plaster rear façade)	Several typologies of original floors (vaulted brick floor / trough vaults / wooden beam structure) +moulded plaster ceilings +	original gable roof with 2 roof trusses and wooden purlins	New contemporary wooden windows	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, doors, staircase	No substantial structural problems or pathologies detected. The building is generally in good condition. Owner complaints about draft and air infiltration through the large window in ROOM1.2 (ground floor back façade).

					Regional Plan (Royal Decree 28/12/1972)+ inventory heritage buildings (Immovable Heritage Decree 12/07/2013 - Section 4)			wooden planks / original and new tiles			etc.) and on street façade.	
HERT	Middle-class townhouse	Building permit 3 April 1914				mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints + exterior insulation on rear façade	Several typologies of floor (vaulted brick floor, composite floor, wooden beam structure) + moulded ceilings+ wooden planks and tiles	gable roof with one roof truss and wooden purlins + annex with flat roof and green roof	Several typologies of windows including original wooden windows (street façade: ground floor + first floor)	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, doors, staircase etc.) and on street façade.	No substantial structural problems or pathologies detected. The building is generally in good condition. -Periodical water infiltration through the floor in the basement. -Air infiltration and draft through the original windows
MARTENS1	Modest house	Early 20th-century				mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with glazed bricks for the street façade / lime mortar joints / rear façade painted outside / plaster in the interior	Several typologies of original floors (trough vaults / wooden beam structure) +(partly) moulded plaster ceilings + wooden planks/ new and original parquet / new and original tiles	gable roof with mansard roof on the street side with 1 roof truss and wooden purlins + 2 annexes with flat roof	New wooden windows based on a historical reference / original wooden windows street façade: 1 + 1 with stained glass	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, plaster consoles, doors, staircase etc.) and on street façade.	The building is generally in very good condition.
MARTENS2	Middle-class townhouse	1909 according to an indication on the facade				mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints / plaster in the interior	Several typologies of original floors (trough vaults / wooden beam structure) +moulded plaster ceilings + original finishing (wooden planks/ parquet / tiles/ mosaic)	gable roof with a mansard shape on the street side and a roof extension at the level of the stairwell at the rear side with wooden purlins + gable roof with one side finished as a hipped roof on the annex (structure unknown)	street façade: wooden windows made according to the original model with thinned double glass / recent wooden windows in the rear façade	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, moulded plaster ceilings, plaster consoles, marble and lin crusta panelling, doors, original marble imitation on a wall, staircase etc.) and on street façade.	The building is generally in very good condition.
KUIPER	Middle-class townhouse	1875-1900	private	Single family house		mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints and natural stone on the exterior of the street façade / plaster in the interior / rear façade and annex with new cement plaster	Several typologies of original floors (trough vaults / wooden beam structure) +moulded plaster ceilings + mostly new finishings / 1 room with original wooden planks	gable roof with mansard roof on the street side - 1 roof truss and wooden purlins + annex with flat roof	All the windows were replaced by plastic windows. The model, material and profiling is standard and not referring to the original.	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, plaster consoles, staircase, doors, etc.) and on street façade.	Good state of conservation (of the construction). A renovation is in progress.
KONING	Middle-class townhouse	Presumably partly dating from the 17th-century with a significant 18th-century renovation and a 19th-century street facade.			CHE-area (Zone regional plan with cultural and/or aesthetic value) according to Regional Plan (Royal Decree 28/12/1972)+ inventory heritage buildings (Immovable Heritage Decree 12/07/2013 - Section 4)	mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints and plaster on both sides	Several typologies of original floors (pressed barrel vaults / cross beam and joists) + moulded plaster ceilings + wooden planks/ parquet / original and new tiles	gable roof with one roof truss and wooden purlins	Wooden windows made according to 19th century model with thinned double glass in the street façade and single glass in the rear façade.	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, doors, staircase etc.) and on street façade.	The entire building is in good condition.
KEIZER	Middle-class townhouse	Building permit 11 November 1842				mixed structure (masonry walls / wooden floors and roof construction / brick vaults)	original solid brick masonry with lime mortar joints and plaster on both sides (exterior: street façade with original lime mortar / rear façade with new cement / annex with original simili-pierre	Several typologies of original floors (vaulted brick floor / wooden beam structure) +moulded plaster ceilings + partly original, partly new finishings (wooden planks/ tiles)	gable roof with one roof truss, wooden purlins and insulation + flat roof (annex)	street facade: partly original wooden windows and door and partly new windows / rear façade: all windows are replaced by wooden or plastic windows	Several valuable elements in the interior (fireplaces, mouldings, doors, staircases etc.) and on street façade.	The building is generally in good condition. There is damage visible on the cement plaster of the back façade: soiled and minor cracks. The sills in bleu stone are deteriorated. Some decay on the roof purlins. The plastering of the rear extension (wall 3) has big cracks and several repairs, probably due to water infiltration. The street façade is in good condition.

Table 3: Summary of the Building Value Assessment and Authenticity section in the Belgian case studies.

Name	VALUE ASSESSMENT						Authenticity
	historical	cultural	social	aesthetic	scientific	architectural	
MEERS	The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century outskirts of the city. The elegant street façade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period and therefore the building has an historical value.					The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century outskirts of the city. The elegant street façade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period and therefore the building has an architectural value.	Except for some elements and finishes, the building has retained its original structure, layout, and decorative exterior and interior elements in their entirety. The addition of glazing beads on some windows and the application of filler on the street façade have slightly impacted the building's authenticity, but these alterations are reversible. The other modifications have caused a limited impact on the heritage value and authenticity of the property. However, these changes are not compatible with the historical architectural style.
BREDERODE	The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 19th-century outskirts of the city. The elegant street façade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period and therefore the building has an historical value. The building is part of an ensemble of 6 identical civic houses that support the heritage value of the street. In a broader context the house forms part of an allotment campaign in the late 19th century, coherent urban project with houses constructed in the same period, all consisting of a similar typology: a neoclassical terraced townhouse with a gable roof.					The architecture of the front façade is typical of the building period. The characterizing elements of its neoclassical style are a plinth in Petit Granit, plaster rendering with a smooth finish, rounded windows, a balcony in natural stone (supported by consoles), and a profiled cornice. The interior layout is typical of the time period: an entry bay with staircase and a second bay with connected salons. The interior decoration is typical of the building period: plaster moulding and ceiling decoration, mantelpieces, original staircase, original flooring	The building has been very mildly renovated over the years, keeping the original layout virtually intact, except for the ground floor addition in the garden. The building structure, internal layout (floors and room division) and circulation have been preserved almost completely. In the interior, many original features have been preserved, such as the mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks, interior doors. The facade itself has been renovated with respect for the original concept and is in good condition. All exterior doors and windows have been replaced with contemporary joinery with a loss of heritage value. Only the window on the ground floor was designed to the original model.
CITADEL	The house was built as part of the urban development of the newly erected boulevard (1875). This boulevard was erected after the dismantling of the ramparts. The plots around this street were developed in the same period, which resulted in a fairly uniform neoclassical terraced houses from the late 19th century and early 20th century, with white-plastered or coloured brick frame facades. However, the redevelopment of the avenue in the 20th century (with more space for cars), resulted in the demolition of numerous 19th century middle-class houses and the construction of multi-family houses, apartment buildings and office buildings along this street. As a result, the avenue has a mixed appearance of 19th century and 20th century buildings. The house was built together with two other houses, construction drawing from 1882. The three houses form an ensemble. The facades of the three houses features plaster rendering decorative window frames, and a rich cornices. Both the typology and the architectural style guaranteed uniformity. The street façade, the building volume, and the			The front façade is in a recognizable neoclassical style with specific elements such as imitation joints, mouldings, continuous drip sills, plinth in bleu stone, profiled wooden cornice.		The architecture of the front façade is typical of the building period. The characterizing elements of its neoclassical style are the plinth in bleu stone plaster rendering with imitation joints on the ground floor and a smooth finish on the upper floors, windows in wood with surround mouldings, continuous drip sills profiled wooden cornice. The front door with above window in wood has specific details. The interior layout is typical of the time period: a smaller bay with vestibule and staircases and next a second bay with connected salons. The interior decoration is typical of the building period: plaster moulding and ceiling decoration, mantelpieces, original staircase.	The building structure of the main volume, internal layout (floors and room division) and circulation have been preserved completely. On the front façade the windows are still authentic, except for the glass, while on the back they have been changed in plastic windows. the windows of the annex are partly original wooden windows, partly new plastic windows. The plasters of the rear façade and annex have heritage value. In the interior (ground floor and first floor) many original features have been preserved, such as the mantelpieces, mouldings, staircase, interior doors. The upper floors are more sober and have originally fewer interior features.

	layout are characteristic for this type of residence in this construction period and therefore the building has an historical value.					
EYCK	The building is a typical example of a 19th-century townhouse. The elegant street façade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period and therefore the building has an historical value.				The building is a typical example of a 19th-century townhouse. The elegant street façade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period and therefore the building has an architectural value.	The main building is authentic. The building structure of the main volume, internal layout (floors and room division) and circulation have been preserved completely. In the interior many original features have been preserved, such as the mantelpieces, mouldings, staircase, interior doors. The veranda is built in 1996. The volume of the kitchen is authentic, but the interior changed in 1996. Except for the windows, the original street façade was kept intact.
MUINK	The house was built as part of the urban development of the southern city, which also included the nearby zoo. Most houses along the street were constructed during the second half of the 19th century as middle-class townhouses with a prominent street façade on and a garden and or warehouse on the back of the building plot. Most of the housing was built in a neoclassical style with a gable roof. The facades feature plaster rendering, decorative window frames, balconies, bay windows and rich cornices. Both the typology and the architectural style guaranteed uniformity. As such, the house forms part of a coherent urban project with houses constructed in the same period, following a similar typology: a neoclassical terraced townhouse with a gable roof.				The architecture of the front façade is typical of the building period. The characterizing elements of its neoclassical style are a plinth in Petit Granit, plaster rendering with smooth-faced rustica on the ground floor and a smooth finish on the upper floors, rounded windows featuring sculpted plaster keystones, a balcony in natural stone (supported by consoles and featuring balusters), a bay window in wood (supported by consoles and featuring pilasters and a cornice) and a profiled cornice on modillions and denticules. The interior layout is typical of the time period: a large entry bay for horse carriages, a smaller (raised) bay with vestibule and staircase and next a third bay with connected salons. The interior decoration is typical of the building period: plaster moulding and ceiling decoration, mantelpieces, original staircase, original flooring, ...	The building has been thoroughly renovated in 2007. In 2010 a roof terrace was added. The changes that have been made, were done with respect to the original concept whilst preserving many of the authentic features. The building structure, internal layout (floors and room division) and circulation have been preserved almost completely. The original architectural concept is thus intact. In the interior, most of the original features have been preserved, such as the mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks, interior doors, chandeliers, etc. The street façade itself has been renovated with respect for the original concept.
HERT	The house was built as part of a large development project of the entire neighbourhood, which was envisioned around 1905-6, on the lands of the former Ghent Zoo, which closed in 1904. The current-day park, in front of the building, is the only remnant of the zoo. The area surrounding the park was developed for housing. As such, the house forms part of a coherent urban project with houses constructed in the same period, following a similar typology: mostly three-storey high terraced houses with a gable roof. Stylistically, both late neoclassical (white plaster rendering) and more eclectic façades featuring (coloured) brickwork were used. The typology and urban layout guaranteed uniformity.				Architecture of the front façade typical of the building period, featuring varied brickwork (patterns and frames of coloured and glazed bricks), façade layout in two bays, great attention to detail, use of Petit Granit natural stone for the plinth (rustica finish) and window/door frames and posts, profiled cornice on modillions, peculiar balcony on iron consoles with decorative wrought iron railing. Interior layout typical of the time period: a large bay of connected salons next to a smaller bay of vertical circulation and service rooms. Interior decoration typical of the building period: plaster moulding and ceiling decoration, mantelpieces, original staircase, original flooring, original windows and doors, original interior woodwork, etched glazing, ...	The building has been renovated several times. The building structure, internal layout (floors and room division) and circulation have been preserved almost completely. The only elements that have been removed, with loss of heritage value, are: mantelpieces in some of the rooms. The street façade itself has been renovated and/or maintained with great attention to detail.
MARTENS1	The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the 20th-century. The elegant street façade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period and therefore the building has an historical value.				The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the early 20th-century. The elegant street facade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period. Therefore, the building has an architectural value.	The building has been renovated on the ground and first floor. The building structure, internal layout (floors and room division) and circulation have been preserved except for some modifications on the ground and first floor. Elements that have been removed, with loss of heritage value, are tiles and parquet in the interior (ground floor and first floor) and the renewing of the iron consoles of the balcony and most of the windows of the street façade. Most likely, moulded plaster ceilings on the first floor were replaced by flat plaster ceilings.

MARTENS2	The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the early 20th-century. The elegant street facade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period. Therefore, the building has an historical value.				The building is a typical example of a townhouse from the early 20th-century. The elegant street facade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period. Therefore, the building has an architectural value.	Apart from some elements and finishes, the building has retained its original structure, layout, and decorative exterior and interior elements in their entirety. The few modifications have only slightly impacted the building's authenticity and some of these alterations are reversible. The street façade itself has been renovated and maintained with great attention to detail.
KUIPER	Inclusion at the inventory of architectural heritage is based on the historical value of the building.				Inclusion at the inventory of architectural heritage is based on the architectural value of the building.	The whole building is authentic and has retained its original structure and layout. The owners are renewing the interior and have removed a lot of finishings. This leads to a loss of heritage values. In the interior most of the original features have been preserved, such as the mantelpieces, mouldings, staircase, interior doors. Except for the windows, the original street façade was kept intact.
KONING	The building is a townhouse believed to date from the 17th century but underwent a significant 18th-century remodelling and was given a 19th-century façade. The house is located in the medieval core of the town. The elegant street façade, the building volume and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction periods and therefore the building has an historical value.				The building is a townhouse believed to date from the 17th century but underwent a significant 18th-century remodelling and was given a 19th-century façade. The house is located in the medieval core of the town. The elegant street façade, the building volume and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction periods and therefore the building has an architectural value.	Except for some elements and finishes, the building has retained its original (17th, 18th, or 19th century) structure, layout, and decorative exterior and interior elements in their entirety. The replacement of the windows in the street and back façades has not affected the heritage value of the building: the replacements were carried out according to the original model. The other changes have had a limited impact on the heritage value and authenticity of the property. Replacements of elements were often done to the original model.
KEIZER	The house was built as part of the urban development of the street (1837-1841). The plots around this street were developed in the same period, which resulted in a fairly homogeneous appearance of plastered and white-painted facades in neo-styles (especially neo-classical) with a balanced rhythmic scenography due to the uniform façade volumes of three or three and a half storeys. The house was built together with two other houses, construction drawing from 1842. The three houses form an ensemble. The facades of the three houses features plaster rendering decorative window frames, bay windows and rich cornices. Both the typology and the architectural style guaranteed uniformity. The street façade, the building volume, and the layout are characteristic of this type of residence for the affluent bourgeoisie from this construction period and therefore the building has an historical value.			The front façade is in a recognizable neoclassical style with specific elements such as imitation joints, mouldings, continuous drip sills, plinth in bleu stone, profiled wooden cornice. Later adaptations on the façade have aesthetic value: bay window including console in stone.	The architecture of the front façade is typical of the building period. The characterizing elements of its neoclassical style are plinth in bleu stone, plaster rendering with imitation joints on the ground floor and a smooth finish on the upper floors, windows in wood with surround mouldings, continuous drip sills and a profiled wooden cornice. The bay window including console in stone is a later adaptation of the façade in y-the same neoclassical style. This element has an aesthetic and architectural value. The front door with authentic, except for the glass. above window in wood has specific details. The original guillotine windows on the ground floors from end 19 th - beginning of the 20th century have original roller shutter with decorative panel on the front façade. The interior layout is typical of the time period: a smaller bay with vestibule and staircases and next a second bay with connected salons. The interior decoration is typical of the building period: plaster moulding and ceiling decoration, mantelpieces, original staircase, original flooring, ... The staircase to the second floor is atypical, but original. It has huge architectural value.	The building structure of the main volume, internal layout (floors and room division) and circulation have been preserved completely. The original architectural concept is thus intact. The rear building (kitchen and bathroom) has been internally renovated and there were adaptations on the exterior (windows), with loss of authenticity. Some of the windows of the street façade are replaced by non-authentic windows. The windows of the ground floor and the bay windows are still authentic, except for the glass. The back façade has its original layout, but the change of rendering has done damage to the authenticity. In the interior (especially on the ground floor), most of the original features have been preserved, such as the mantelpieces, mouldings, floor planks, interior doors and staircases. The upper floors are more sober and have originally fewer interior features. Especially on the third floor elements have been removed.

4. Norway: application in case studies

Authors: Cecilie Flyen (NIKU) and Lars Jacob Hvinden-Haug (NIKU)

4.1. Case studies overview

The testing of the summary sheet has been focused on three timber log and timber frame construction case studies in the city of Trondheim, as listed in the following.

Table 4: Summary of the testing phase method in the Norwegian case studies.

Case studies	Archetype	Survey method	Survey team
Nedre1 	Town house with courtyard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite inspection and analysis • Collection of drawings from the municipal archives • Archival research • Heritage board consultation • Technical installations data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NIKU group
Nedre2 	Town house with courtyard and warehouse with wharf	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite inspection and analysis • Collection of drawings from the municipal archives • Archival research • Heritage board consultation • Technical installations data collection 	
Nygata 	Town house with courtyard, detached	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite inspection and analysis • Collection of drawings from the municipal archives • Archival research • Heritage board consultation • Technical installations data collection 	

4.2. Main findings of application results

After compiling the Summary Sheet for each case study, all collected data has been summarized into two tables: one indicating all information related to the Building Identity

Cards of the Norwegian case studies (Table 5) and another for collecting information on their Building Value Assessment and identification of Authenticity (Table 6). This process of synthesizing descriptive data has made it possible to clarify possible similarities between different cases, however present in the same city and therefore in the same climatic and geographical context.

In addition to several buildings in Bakklandet having significant individual heritage value, all historic structures featuring timber log and timber frame construction are themselves of high cultural importance. These construction methods should remain untouched due to their intrinsic heritage value.

Moreover, the entire historic environment forms part of a protected neighbourhood. The area is subject to a heritage protection plan and is also designated as a cultural heritage zone under a special zoning provision in the municipal spatial plan. As a result, the buildings are valued not only for their individual significance but also as integral components of a cohesive urban landscape.

Consequently, elements such as structural form, scale in relation to the street, and spatial relationships with neighbouring buildings are also protected. These restrictions limit the extent of permissible alterations, even for newer buildings. Such considerations are crucial for both existing structures with varying degrees of heritage value and for newer developments that have replaced earlier buildings. Any intervention should be discussed with the Urban Conservation Office in Trondheim municipality, prior to applying for a building permit.

What emerged from the Norwegian cases is mainly that:

Nedre1

- Located close to the bridge Bybrua, this house is one of the oldest in the Bakklandet district in Trondheim. Traced back to 1766, the building was originally an unpanelled timber house with a turf roof and leaded glass windows, a stable, and a woodshed of panelled half-timber in the back yard. The main building had a two-room plan with a half-timbered gallery towards the yard and a servants' chamber on the other side of the gateway. There was a kitchen fireplace, an iron stove and a soapstone stove. On the second floor there was a chamber and attic. In 1926, the house was extended to a full second floor with an apartment, and north of the gateway downstairs was a milk shop. The windows and panels were replaced inside and out. The roof was covered with slate.
The present café (ground floor) was established in the building in 1997, as a transformation from the prior use as a dwelling.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as *HV_III.1 Highly valuable facades with low valuable windows*. This building has been subjected to interventions. The building holds high heritage/antiquarian value (level B) on the municipal cultural heritage map, although it is not formally listed. The building's street-facing façade is of significant heritage value, with original cladding and gate, and must remain untouched. The rear façade also holds high value. The visible roof, featuring original materials, is considered valuable; where materials have been replaced, restoration is encouraged. Alterations on the rear side of the building are generally more acceptable, as they have less impact on the visual coherence of the neighbourhood.

The windows were replaced in the 1980's and may be fully replaced since they are not original. New, energy-efficient windows should replicate the historical design. Some interior elements are of value, particularly walls, floors, and ceilings, which should be preserved. However, since the interior is not listed, low-impact and reversible interventions are permitted.

Nedre2

- Nedre2 was built in 1845 when a previous building of the same size was demolished. The house was of the more important type in Bakklandet as it is situated by the river. It is built of panelled log timber with a tiled roof and a basement, which is not common. The dwelling building has two rather high floors with a typical four-room plan and a gate to the yard. At that time, the rooms also got new panelling. The attic was converted into an apartment. Also, the main staircase probably dates from this time. Later, the windows to the street were changed into modern types. In the 1980-ies there was a wish from the heritage council to list the complex as a well-preserved example of its type, but did not succeed. In 2014 and 2019 it was instead rebuilt into 11 new apartments including the warehouse. The warehouse with wharf has not been inspected and/or assessed.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as *HV_III.2 Valuable front facade with low valuable windows*. The building has high heritage/antiquarian value (Level B on the municipal cultural heritage map). It is however not listed.

The building has already undergone several interventions. Its elegant classicist entrance, featuring pilasters and architraves, has been preserved along with the exterior cladding on the front façade. Inside, a few finely crafted doors remain. In 2014 and 2019, the building – including the former warehouse – was converted into 11 new apartments.

The street-facing façade is of high heritage value, retaining its original gate and cladding, as well as a notable staircase in the rear courtyard. While the rear façade holds some heritage significance, previous renovations in the 1980s—including replacement of cladding and windows—have reduced its historical integrity. As a result, more extensive modifications may be permitted on the rear side.

The windows may be fully replaced, as they are not original. New, energy-efficient windows should replicate the historical design and appearance and should be reinstated in a manner consistent with the original historical design and use of materials. Certain interior elements, such as walls, floors, and ceilings, are of heritage value and should be preserved.

Nygata

- Nygata was originally the site of a cow stable of the 19th century and later, the building was horizontally arranged into two apartments. The house has two relatively high floors, each with a three-part plan, and with a fine cornice-shaped gutter and a hipped roof. The dwelling house is constructed of log timber and panelled outside and inside (originally not panelled towards the yard). The timber construction rests on a foundation ring wall of natural stone of small dimensions, plastered. Towards the crawlspace and the attic there is a stub-floor with a layer of clay between the beams for insulation.

- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as *HV_II. Highly valuable façade with typical valuable interior elements*. The building is of high heritage/antiquarian value (level B) on the municipal cultural heritage map), however not listed.

The building has already undergone several alterations. The street-facing façades are of high heritage value, featuring original cladding that must remain untouched. Historically, the windows likely featured small panes facing the courtyard and larger panes facing the street—typical of early 19th-century design. In 1958, the windows were replaced. Although the windows are not original, they are considered to have heritage significance and may be subject to only minor, reversible interventions. They consist of old wooden frames with single glazing and some of them have internal single casement windows.

The rear façade, including its windows, also holds high heritage value. The visible roofscape is significant, and both the façade and its proportions must be preserved. The original roofing may be reinstated, or the roof may be resurfaced in accordance with the original design. Some interior elements are of value and should be preserved, although minor, reversible interventions are permitted.

The roof was previously covered with corrugated sheets. By the late 20th century, the building had fallen into disrepair but has since been partially restored. The exterior cladding appears to be original. Inside, some doors and panelling have been preserved, though a few doors are reclaimed historic elements from other buildings. The attic has recently been converted into a bedroom by the owner, and the ground floor apartment is currently rented out.

Table 5: Summary of the Building Identity Card section in the Norwegian case studies.

Name	ARCHETYPE	CONSTRUCTION PERIOD	OWNER	ACTUAL USE	LEGAL CONSTRAINTS	MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES						STATE OF CONSERVATION
						Structure	Wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	Interiors elements	
Nedre1	Town house with courtyard	Built after 1718, changed last time 1926	Privately owned by a property developer and management company	A café and a small shop on the ground floor. Two apartments on the first floor	According to municipal cultural heritage map Level B/high antiquarian value	The timber construction rests on a foundation ring wall of natural stone of small dimensions, plastered	Log timber structure and panelled outside and inside. Layers: Outer panel, timber, partly bevelled/chamfered panel, partly modern bead staff panel, and partly other modern boards.	Front building has a gable roof. Shed roof on the wings. Roof layers: Slate towards the street, the rest are PVC roof membrane, battens, tar paper, wooden boards +Two chimneys originating from 1926	Stub wooden floor with clay/stub ceiling (not more original) towards cold attic probably with insulation	Original windows were lead windows, later lattice windows. Modern windows from the 1990's are medium-quality copies of later windows from 1926	The shop and the gateway have bevelled/chamfered panel kept (from 1926) One 18th Century door in upstairs apartment, with high quality rococo profiles	The building complex was renovated in 1997 to 2000; there are some visible damage points (water board above window and panel in back yard damaged by rot decay, and on the main gate towards ground)
Nedre2	Town house with courtyard and warehouse with wharf	Dwelling (front building towards the street) 1845 and warehouse 1852 (towards the river)	Privately owned. Individual owners of flats, joint ownership of courtyard and other joint areas	11 apartments	According to municipal cultural heritage map: Front building, level B/antiquarian value; Warehouse building, level B/high antiquarian value	The timber construction rests on a foundation ring wall of natural stone of small dimensions, plastered. There is a basement under a part of the house. The two wings in the yard are half-timbered and panelled outside and inside. It rests on a simple stone foundation.	Log timber structure and panelled outside and inside. The original warehouse with wharf is half-timbered and panelled outside. Layers: Outer panel, timber, partly bevelled/chamfered panel, partly modern bead staff panel, and partly other modern boards.	Front building has a gable roof. Truncated hip roof on the warehouse. Shed roof on the wings. Roof layers: Brick tiles, battens, tar paper, wooden boards, aeration layer, insulation, inner panel boards	Stub wooden floor with clay/stub ceiling probably with insulation. Later parquet and linoleum/vinyl, ceiling gypsum boards and paint	No original windows left, except from a few staircase windows in the back yard The original, removed windows were lattice windows of the classical type Modern windows from the 1980's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Two original doors in ground floor apartment (only one apartment inspected/accessed) •Original iron inspection hatch for/in chimney •Wall panel, partly later 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Moisture problems in basement •Retrofitting may have introduced elements increasing the rot decay risk in the construction
Nygata	Town house with courtyard, detached	1824-1827	Privately owned	Two apartments, one on each floor	According to municipal cultural heritage map Level B/high antiquarian value	The timber construction rests on a foundation ring wall of natural stone of small dimensions, plastered. The shed in the backyard rests on simple stone foundations.	Log timber structure and panelled outside and inside. Layers: Outer panel, timber, partly bead staff panel and partly modern boards. Exterior panel are probably original	Front building has a hipped roof. Shed roof on the shed. Roof layers: Corrugated metal sheets, battens, tar paper, wooden boards. Earlier cold roof, recently insulated, added aeration, membrane, and boards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ground floor: Original stub floor with clay removed. Recently insulated floor with hydronic heating all over ground floor apartment, with parquet. •Ceiling towards attic: stub ceiling towards cold attic probably with insulation 	No old windows left. Original latticed windows changed in 1958	The are some original and older details preserved. This includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Older bead staff wall panel and ceiling on first floor - Original doors, one upstairs and one downstairs to staircase - Original floorboards on first floor - Original staircase 	The apartment on the ground floor was renovated in 2009 and partly recently (2024); however, shed in back yard have some visible, superficial rot decay and the construction may have some structural defects

Table 6: Summary of the Building Value Assessment and Authenticity section in the Norwegian case studies.

Name	VALUE ASSESSMENT						Authenticity
	historical	Cultural	social	aesthetic	scientific	architectural	
Nedre1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Erik Digre was the first of the family of the important Jacob Digre construction company Typical for its type in the area, and one of the older buildings of the neighbourhood - and thus of high interest It can be followed in archives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Part of historical neighbourhood and thus an important element as a part of a whole As a part of the neighbourhood - and development history/process, it has tangible and intangible value 	Local significance as meeting place (the café) and as part of a street scape and neighbourhood of high value	Presence of decorative elements (shopfront and gate with its pilasters and architrave, old exterior panel of the 1926)		Important architectural elements, structure, volumes, placing of building components etc. are in line with the neighbourhood, fulfilling a role as a part of a whole	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gate and panel towards street are old and thus authentic Change of windows have not taken the authenticity of the building into huge consideration thus the authenticity of the building is reduced due to this change The entrance from the street seems to be old with old panelling on walls and ceiling First floor apartment in front building has an 18th century door in the interiors
Nedre2	Typical for its type in the area, and thus interesting and can be followed in archives	As a part of the wharf system and warehouse development history/process, it has intangible value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Part of a street scape and neighbourhood of high value It was seized as enemy property by the German SD in 1942 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Important element in the totality of the street scape and neighbourhood Original classical gate and panelling and staircase in courtyard of high quality 		Important architectural elements, structure, volumes, placing of building components etc. are in line with the neighbourhood, fulfilling a role as a part of a whole	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The complex is heavily restored and partly restructured (concrete stilts have replaced original timber stilts), but some construction elements have been preserved: Gate and panel towards street are original and thus authentic Façade towards river has uphold the impression of a warehouse, and main parts of the construction has high authenticity Change of windows have not taken the authenticity of the building into huge consideration, thus the authenticity of the building is reduced due to this change The entrance from the street seems to be original, with original panelling on walls and in ceiling Ground floor apartment in front building has partly older panels and original doors in the interiors Staircase in backyard, probably from 1900, is well preserved.
Nygata	Typical for its type in the area, and thus interesting and can be followed in archives	Part of historical neighbourhood and thus an important element as a part of a whole		It is an important element in the totality of the street scape and neighbourhood	Timber log construction is naturally ventilated between logs, and yields a relatively good insulation effect	Important architectural elements, structure, volumes, placing of building components etc. are in line with the neighbourhood, fulfilling a role as a part of a whole	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main parts of the construction seem to be original in the interior First floor apartment has old panel and a couple of original, preserved doors

5. Estonia: application in case studies

Author(s): Üllar Alev (MKA)

5.1. Case studies overview

The testing of the summary sheet has been focused on 5 building in Tallinn, as listed in the following.

Table 7: Summary of the testing phase method in the Estonian case studies.

Case studies	Archetype	Survey method	Survey team
Kristiina 	Stalinist brick apartment building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Archival research • Technical installations data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MKA (building identity card and value assessment) • TalTech (technical installations data collection)
Sikupilli 	Stalinist brick apartment building		
Pilve 	Tallinn type wooden apartment building		
Koidu 	Tallinn type wooden apartment building		
Komeedi 	Wooden apartment building		

5.2. Main findings of application results

After compiling the Summary Sheet for each case study, all collected data has been summarized into two tables: one indicating all information related to the Building Identity Cards of the Estonian case studies (Table 8) and another for collecting information on their Building Value Assessment and identification of Authenticity (Table 9). This process of synthesizing descriptive data has made it possible to clarify possible similarities between different cases, however present in the same city and therefore in the same climatic and geographical context.

What emerged from the Estonian cases is mainly that:

KRISTIINA

- The building is in a milieu-valuable area of Uus-Maailm and is part of an ensemble forming two almost complete quarters that follow the urban planning principles of the Soviet era. It was built in 1958 and corresponds to the Stalinist brick apartment building archetype. The building is larger than other Estonian case-study buildings, with four floors and a basement. The walls of the building are of brick masonry, while the plinth is made of limestone. The structures have largely remained original, although the façade plaster was repaired and repainted 14 years ago. The plastered façade is rich in architectural details typical of this building period. The basement was initially used for storage but has been converted into bicycle parking.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. The façade plaster is original, and the foundation wall is authentic; therefore, external insulation is not an option, except for a thin layer on the back façade, which has fewer decorative details. The attic is unused, and its floor has already been insulated using blown wool. Most of the windows have been replaced with modern PVC ones of different types. All the windows can be replaced with new ones to achieve a consistent appearance for the house. New wooden windows can feature energy-efficient glazing.

SIKUPIILLI

- The building is in a milieu-valuable area of Sikupilli and a part of a milieu-valuable ensemble. The buildings in the Sikupilli milieu-valuable area are built between 1940-1950 and follow the principles of Stalinist era urban planning and neo-classicist aesthetics. The construction projects used came from architects from Russia, not locally. The case study building lacks the rich décor of similar houses nearby built some years earlier as cost efficiency was becoming more prioritized.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_III. The masonry walls of the building used to contain an air cavity, which has now been filled with urea foam (ca 5 years ago) to conserve energy and improve thermal comfort. Attic and basement have been partly converted to extensions of 2nd and 1st floor apartments respectively. Insulation in the attic is suspected to be lacking due to low thermal comfort both in winter and summer. 1 apartment has installed interior insulation. During the facade restoration ca 5 years ago, the basement walls were waterproofed and insulated from the outside. In conclusion many energy-efficiency works have been implemented that have already changed the appearance of the house. Finishing layers have been mostly replaced, but the size of the house is preserved, and architectural details are restored. The replaced

windows are different from originals. Replacement of already replaced windows with more energy efficient ones can be considered if needed. Roof cover has been replaced with unsuitable material (corrugated steel roofing), it can be replaced with a new and more appropriate one, with an upgraded insulation layer beneath the roof to be installed concurrently.

PILVE

- The building is of Tallinn type wooden apartment building and the walls are made of horizontal logs. However, the facades have been covered with a plaster layer on top of a wooden boarding, which is separated from the log wall with an air gap and tar paper. Façade plaster is original. Attic is converted to apartments, while basement is currently unheated and contains storage spaces (although has previously been used as living space too). Foundation wall is authentic but needs replastering. Roof cover is replaced with suitable roofing material and attic floor is converted to apartments.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. The replaced windows are in good condition, but different from restored originals. Replacement of already replaced windows with more energy efficient ones can be considered if needed. Interior insulation is used in some apartments, and it can be added to walls that currently lack an interior insulation layer.

KOIDU

- The building is of Tallinn type wooden apartment building and the walls are made of horizontal logs. However, the façade wooden cladding together with window trim boards are replaced. Some apartments have applied interior insulation. Foundation wall is authentic and repaired. The attic has been converted to apartments along with installing new roofing and insulation. The basement is currently used as storage spaces, and contains a sauna, while it has previously also housed a small shop. The floor between the basement and first floor is partly insulated with cellulose insulation. The windows are a mix of restored original, soviet era and modern windows with varying condition and performance.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as as HV_III. Wooden cladding of the facade is already replaced with suitable new one (authentic boarding is lost) and therefore it can be considered to add a thin layer of external insulation behind the cladding if needed. The plinth wall is without plaster (exposed limestone blocks) and should be kept this way. The roof has been recently replaced with new suitable solution and insulation between rafters has been added already. The windows have been partly replaced with new ones slightly different from original ones. Replacement of already replaced windows with more energy efficient ones can be considered if needed. Interior insulation is used in some apartments, and it can be added to walls that currently lack an interior insulation layer.

KOMEEDI

- Although not being a typical Lender or Tallinn type wooden apartment building, the solutions and era are similar to the archetype. Compared to the Tallinn type building, the staircase is wooden, not masonry. The walls are made of horizontal logs and are

covered with wooden cladding. The building was constructed in two stages (hence 2 construction dates) and initially housed the owner's family.

- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_III. Although the wooden cladding of the facade is original, a thin layer of external insulation can be added behind the cladding, reusing the original wooden boards as much as possible. The plinth wall is without plaster (exposed limestone blocks) and should be kept this way. As the current roof covering (corrugated steel roof) is not suitable for this house, it can be replaced with a new and more appropriate one, with an upgraded insulation layer beneath the roof to be installed concurrently. The windows have been partly replaced with modern ones of different types, qualities, and performances. All the windows can be replaced with similar ones to achieve a consistent appearance for the house. New wooden double-frame windows can feature energy-efficient glazing in the inner frame. Interior insulation is used in some apartments, and it can be added to walls that currently lack an interior insulation layer.

Table 8: Summary of the Building Identity Card section in the Estonian case studies.

Name	ARCHETYPE	CONSTRUCTION PERIOD	OWNER	ACTUAL USE	LEGAL CONSTRAINTS	MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES						STATE OF CONSERVATION
						Structure	Wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	Interiors elements	
Kristiina	Stalinist brick apartment building	1958	private	residential	Milieu valuable area according to Planning Act	Brick walls on top of limestone thick foundation, concrete floor slabs	Original silicate brick walls plastered from both sides	Hip roof with replaced cover of tile form metal sheets	Concrete floor slabs	The original double-framed windows are made of wood. Most of the windows have been replaced with different PVC windows.	Not protected and evaluated	Main structures seem to be in good condition. Few cracks on walls can be found. Façade is renovated.
Sikupilli	Stalinist brick apartment building	1958			Milieu valuable area according to Planning Act	Brick walls on top of limestone thick foundation, concrete floor slabs	Walls are made of silicate bricks and plastered from both sides. All cavities in the masonry are filled with thermal insulation.	Gable roof made with corrugated metal sheets. The roof is insulated between the rafters.	Concrete floor slabs	Most of the windows have been replaced with different PVC windows. Windows of one apartment are replaced with replicas of original timber windows.	Not protected and evaluated	Main structures are in good condition. Façade is renovated.
Pilve	Tallinn type wooden apartment building	ca 1940			Milieu valuable area according to Planning Act	Horizontal log walls on top of limestone foundation, wooden floor and roof constructions	Most of the walls are made of horizontal logs covered with a plaster layer on top of a wooden boarding, some walls have old 50 mm wood wool cement board as external insulation under plaster layer. In many rooms additional old finishing layers have been removed and the load-bearing log wall surface is exposed as interior finishing. Staircase walls are made of bricks.	Clipped gable roof covered with new standing seam metal roofing. Large dormers on both sides.	Wooden floor beams, sand or concrete between the beams. Finishing of oak or laminate parquet.	The original double-framed windows are made of wood. Some of the wooden windows are restored and most of the windows have been replaced with different windows	Not protected and evaluated	Main structures seem to be in good condition. Foundation needs replastering and wall plaster repairing. One section of the plinth is replastered using decorative finishing (stone blocks imitation).
Koidu	Tallinn type wooden apartment building	1931			Milieu valuable area according to Planning Act	Horizontal log walls on top of limestone foundation, wooden floor and roof constructions	Most of the walls are made of horizontal logs, some of the walls have interior fibrous insulation layer of 5 cm. Staircase walls are made of bricks.	Hip roof made of standing seam metal sheets, large hip dormers on both hip-ends. Roof construction has insulation between rafters.	First floor of reinforced concrete, upper floors on wooden beams, mineral wool between the beams. Finishing of laminate parquet (on top of OSB board) or wooden floor boarding.	The original double-framed windows are made of wood. Most of the windows have been replaced with slightly different windows.	Not protected and evaluated	Main structures seem to be in good condition.
Komeedi	Tallinn type wooden apartment building	1932			Milieu valuable area according to Planning Act	Horizontal log walls on top of limestone foundation, wooden floor and roof constructions	Walls are made of horizontal logs	Clipped gable roof covered with corrugated steel roofing. Large flat wall dormer on south side and gable wall dormer on south side. Roof construction has insulation between rafters.	First floor of reinforced concrete, upper floors on wooden beams, mineral wool between the beams. Finishing of laminate parquet or wooden floor boarding.	The original double-framed windows are made of wood. Most of the windows have been replaced with slightly different windows	Not protected and evaluated	Main structures seem to be in good condition.

Table 9: Summary of the Building Value Assessment and Authenticity section in the Estonian case studies.

Name	VALUE ASSESSMENT						Authenticity
	historical	Cultural	social	aesthetic	scientific	architectural	
Kristiina	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Representative of Stalinist residential architecture post-WWII (1958) Designed by renowned Estonian architect Alar Kotli. 	<p>Locally protected as a valuable building</p> <p>Located in a historically significant urban area rebuilt after 1944 bombing</p>	Symbolic of Soviet-era urban reconstruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stylized plaster façade, original eave cornices, and small balconies. Harmonious proportions and decorative plaster frames 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thick masonry walls with cavity (ash fill); passive thermal mass. Original design includes unheated attic as a thermal buffer. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Milieu-type Stalinist apartment block. External finishes and details exemplify era's design aesthetics 	<p>Façade plaster is original and foundation wall is authentic. The replaced windows are different from originals. Roof cover is replaced with unsuitable material.</p>
Sikupilli	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Representative of Stalinist residential architecture post-WWII (1958) 	<p>Locally protected as a valuable building</p> <p>Located in a historically significant urban area rebuilt after 1944 bombing</p>	Symbolic of Soviet-era urban reconstruction	Valuable historic balcony on front-façade		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A typical milieu area house with some interior decorative elements that have been restored 	<p>Finishing layers have been mostly replaced, but the size of the house is preserved and architectural details are restored. The replaced windows are different from originals. Roof cover is replaced with unsuitable material.</p>
Pilve	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Built ca. 1940; part of typical Tallinn wooden housing development. Reflects late pre-war architecture and continuity with older types 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Located in milieu-protected central area of Tallinn. Protected under city thematic planning 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastered log walls, clipped gable roof with dormers. Original aesthetic largely preserved in form and materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dormers and insulated roof improve passive climate control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preserves typical elements: log structure, compact form, plaster finish. Valuable as type specimen of its era and locality 	<p>Façade plaster is original. Foundation wall is authentic, but needs replastering. Roof cover is replaced with suitable roofing material and attic floor is converted to apartments. The replaced windows are in good condition, but different from restored originals.</p>
Koidu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It belongs to a period of significance (interwar architecture, 1931) It has documentary evidence through records (1930s Tallinn city maps) The building reflects urban expansion trends in Tallinn during the interwar period and housing development linked to railway and industrial growth. 	<p>Locally protected as a valuable building under thematic planning</p>	It has local significance as a residential building type forming part of Tallinn's pre-war wooden housing stock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Façade in traditional wooden cladding with log structure underneath (typical Tallinn wooden building design). Original front door and windows preserved in parts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thick log walls with thermal mass Hip roof aiding drainage and attic ventilation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A typical milieu area house 	<p>Façade wooden cladding together with window trim boards are replaced. Foundation wall is authentic and repaired. Roof cover is replaced and attic floor is converted to apartments.</p>
Komeedi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Belongs to interwar housing development (1932). Documented in 1930s maps and part of post-WWI urban planning in Tallinn 	<p>Locally protected as a valuable building</p> <p>Protected by thematic planning (Tallinn City Council decision No. 78/2009)</p>		Timber cladding, dormers, and historic wooden structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Passive strategies include: log walls, insulated pitched roof, compact form. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A typical milieu area house Representative example of Tallinn wooden apartment buildings. Limestone plinth and log structure are valuable elements. 	<p>Façade wooden cladding is original. Foundation wall is authentic and repaired. Roof cover is replaced with unsuitable corrugated steel roof. The replaced windows are different from originals.</p>

6. Italy: application in case studies

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6.1. Case studies overview

The testing of the summary sheet has been focused on four different and prevalent archetypes of masonry buildings in the UNESCO area of Mantova, as listed in the following.

Table 10: Summary of the testing phase method in the Italian case studies.

Case studies	Archetype	Survey method	Survey team
MONTANARA 	Palazzetto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Collection of drawings from the architect • Archival research • Heritage board consultation • Energy data collection • Monitoring data 	
GIULIO ROMANO 	Gothic lot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Collection of drawings from the architect • Archival research • Heritage board consultation • Monitoring data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PoliMI group (building identity card and value assessment) • ZH (technical installations data collection) • EURAC (monitoring data activity)
LEONARDO 	Extended building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Geometrical survey • Archival research • Church institution consultation • Energy data collection • Monitoring data 	
VESCOVILE 	Courtyard building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onsite analysis • Collection of drawings from the church institution • Bibliographic research • Monitoring data 	

6.2. Main findings of application results

After compiling the Summary Sheet for each case study, all collected data has been summarized into two tables: one indicating all information related to the Building Identity Card of the Italian case studies (Table 11) and another for collecting information on their Building Value Assessment and identification of Authenticity (Table 12). This process of synthesizing descriptive data has made it possible to clarify possible similarities between different cases, however present in the same city and therefore in the same climatic and geographical context.

What emerged from the Italian cases is mainly that:

MONTANARA

- Building from the early 17th century, it corresponds to the Palazzetto archetype. It is subject to a landscape constraint of the UNESCO area. With three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic, the building has a three-openings rhythm on the facade, without presenting any other decoration. An internal courtyard/garden at the back allows the rooms to gain more sunlight. The rooms are mostly frescoed, and the plaster false ceiling has a reed grip structure underneath.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. This building, in fact, has in fact preserved its valuable elements on the main façade as well as its interior decorations with frescoes and its historic roof. However, it has already been subject of partial interior interventions. At the same time, a part of the windows and all those on the backyard were replaced in the 80s with wooden frames and double glazing. It is conceivable, therefore, to work to replace recent windows and doors with more compatible and high-performance ones. Interior retrofit may be carefully evaluated. Solution at roof level from inside may be suggested. Improvement solutions to restore the ancient ventilation passive system of the wind tower - closed in recent years with a metal frame - may also be allowed.

GIULIO ROMANO

- Gothic lot building with an internal courtyard, having three levels. The building retains the characteristics of a neoclassical construction with solid raw bricks, wooden floors, a plaster and reed false ceiling, and an underlying wattle structure. Part of the first and second floor (those overlooking the courtyard) were rebuilt as a brick and concrete slab in the 1950s after being damaged during the WWII. The facade features a pair of openings, with the historic wooden door still serving as the entrance today. From it, one enters a long corridor leading to the internal courtyard at the rear.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_III. Despite the presence of some historic construction elements (e.g. the reed gypsum mortar ceilings), this building has already been subject of huge interior renovation interventions. No longer in use, almost all windows have been changed in recent years - except for the entrance door at the groundfloor which is of the XIX century. The shutters, on the other hand, have all been restored on the main front and some on the internal front have been made like the ancient ones. Interior floors have been partially preserved, except for the 50s wing which is in cement boards. According to this discontinuity, it would be appropriate to verify the building structural compatibility in response to earthquakes, so interventions on the

horizontal levels may be acceptable. Interior walls have been recently plastered, so interior wall interventions may be considered as well.

LEONARDO

- Building from the early 16th century, it corresponds to the archetype of the extended building with a linear distribution of rooms and common spaces along a central corridor. The staircase is located at the end of this corridor. Constructed of solid bricks and wooden floors. Rooms are distributed vertically via a stone staircase with shaped steps of architectural and historical value. The ground floor presents a living room with a kitchen and three rooms which are full-time occupied. Fragments of frescoes from the late 16th century are visible on the walls at both ground and first floor. The attic, non-accessible and pillared, has a double-pitched roof with a very high inter-storey space. All rooms have brick vaults and are used as common spaces, with small windows that open.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_II. Although the building was modified in the 19th century, the difference between the old portion of the 16th century and the other is not perceptible today, except for the presence in many rooms of original decorated wooden ceilings and frescoes on the walls. In the rest of the building, plaster has covered the different layers, and the building has also been subject of retrofit interventions. The basement, which maintains its original configuration, would require a dehumidification improvement for solving the presence of rising damp. The roof has been restored in recent years, but not yet insulated, as it would be desirable. Moreover, almost all windows have double glass and restored shading systems.

VESCOVILE

- The Vescovile Palace of Mantova was built in the mid-18th century on ancient 14th century buildings and completed in 1765 by the Bianchi marquises (Introini and Spinelli, 2018). The building has three levels, plus a basement and an attic, and internal spaces overlook the internal eccentric courtyard. The building is actually used by the curia, and it has the diocesan historical archive in the basement. The first floor, dedicated to housing, has an apartment with 5 bedrooms.
- The case study falls under the Heritage value scenario identified in document D5.4 as HV_I. The building preserves its unique elements, and interior surfaces are highly valuable with a spectacular pincer staircase and vaulted ceilings decorated with stucco and frescoes. The imposing facade spanning eleven lights is divided horizontally into three bands by string course frames: the smooth ashlar covering the lower band also frames the external and three central bays for the entire height. All brick facades are quite symmetrical and have wooden windows, internal tents and external wooden shading systems. However, in the residential area some changes have been made over time to accommodate a group of nuns who until recent times lived on the residential floor: insertion of partitions, creation of bathrooms and kitchen rooms, addition of a new double glass in the existing wooden window frames. So, interventions on windows and minimum low-impact solutions in the interior may be considered as possible.

Table 11: Summary of the Building Identity Card section in the Italian case studies.

Name	ARCHETYPE	CONSTRUCTION PERIOD	OWNER	ACTUAL USE	LEGAL CONSTRAINTS	MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES						STATE OF CONSERVATION
						Structure	Wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	Interiors elements	
MONTANARA	Palazzetto	17th century	PRIVATE	Residential	UNESCO protection area; PGT Areas with very high landscape sensitivity - Properties worthy of protection: grade 3 constraint; A2: Suburb of the first and second circle, art. D43, D44, D45	Plastered brick load-bearing masonry. It seems to do not have problems of stability, except for the roof that has been reinforced with brick pillars.	Brickwork from 17th century with small integrations in the upper levels. The façade located on the internal courtyard has numerous points of humidity .	Double-pitched roof with wooden planking, joists and wooden beams+ancient turret for the ventilation of the building	Wooden floorboard resting on a framework of joists and main beams+false ceiling is made of reed and plaster mortar and is characterized by oval decorative stuccoes	New wooden windows+original shutters (only one 17th century window in the attic floor)	Under the recent plaster there are frescoes dating back to the late 19th century.	Currently the building is in a state of neglect: it is not inhabited, and the new owners have begun to carry out just some exploratory surveys to understand more about the construction system and materials. Despite this, the structure is in excellent condition. Only in some rooms some false ceilings have been removed. The roof above the staircase, which once served as a wind tower in the summer, is closed with a metal frame that may require some recovery or replacement, to restore the ancient passive system.
GIULIO ROMANO	Gothic Lot	18th-19th century; partial reconstruction of the XX century			Art. 45 L. 42/2004 (ex-art. 21 L. 1089/39) - Indirect regulatory constraint; PGT Art. D16 - A3 Areas with characteristics of continuity with the UNESCO area	Plastered brick load-bearing masonry + 50s addition facing the internal courtyard in concrete slabs and brick walls.	Plastered brickwork in raw bricks from 18th century+ brickwork with cooked brick in the 50s wing. Both main façade and internal façade have been recently covered by plaster, with a base in cement mortar	Double-pitched roof with wooden planking, joists and wooden beams	Wooden floor+composite floor (50s wing)	Some historic openings were preserved at the groundfloor+new ones+historic shutters (similar in the 50s wing)	A well-made staircase with cantilevered stone steps of the first 20th century in cement tiles and red stone, covered by a wind tower. Original wooden floors and false ceilings in reed and gypsum mortar. Internal partitions are recent.	Currently the building is in a state of neglect: it is not inhabited, and the new owners have begun to carry out just some exploratory surveys to understand more about the construction system and materials. Despite this, the structure is in good condition. Windows frames are not in good conditions at the groundfloor, where the situation seems worst; at first and second floor in some rooms false ceilings have been removed . The roof above the staircase, which once served as a wind tower in the summer, is closed with a metal frame that may require some recovery or replacement, to restore the ancient passive system.
LEONARDO	Extended Building	16th century	CHURCH PROPERTY	Residential / youth center	art. 10 L. 42/2004 (ex-art. 1 L. 1089/39) - Direct protection	Plastered brick load-bearing masonry	Brick load-bearing masonry from 16th century with integrations in the following centuries on the northwest part	Double-pitched roof with wooden planking, joists and wooden beams	Wooden floor	New windows	Frescoes at the upper part of walls+decoration on woden beams of the wooden floors	According to the fact that the building is used to host young people spending period in connection with the church activities, for long or short terms, it is in good conditions, except for the back façade and the presence of high humidity in the cellar.
VESCOVILE	Courtyard Building	1756		Residential (1 st floor), Offices (ground floor), diocesan archives (underground)	art. 10 L. 42/2004 (ex-art. 1 L. 1089/39) - Direct protection	Plastered brick load-bearing masonry	Brick load-bearing masonry of 80cm thickness	Double-pitched roof with wooden planking, joists and wooden beams	Vaulted ceilings+wooden floors+stuccoes	Historic/new windows with double glazing	High valuable frescoes in the vaults in some rooms of the residential part, as well as one small chapel	The building is kept in a good state of preservation in the residential area. Despite several changes occurred during times for partitioning original spaces into smaller rooms and creating also toilets, original floors and decorations were maintained

Table 12: Summary of the Building Value Assessment and Authenticity section in the Italian case studies.

Name	VALUE ASSESSMENT						Authenticity
	historical	Cultural	social	aesthetic	scientific	architectural	
MONTANARA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •It belongs to the 17th century •It has documentary evidence through historic maps (i.e. Ranieri's map) 	It is part of the Mantova-historic centre.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inside there are numerous relevant elements: frescoes of different dates, reed ceilings with stuccoes from the late '800. Nothing remains inside of the antique furniture. •The building is part of the building curtain of the seventeenth-century historic centre of Mantua. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The presence of a wind tower and a double courtyard (internal and external) allowed for improved ventilation and lighting within the lot. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Inside the building we find a 17th century walled window that demonstrates the ancient use of the wind tower, once without a roof. •Of great importance is the false ceiling system with hand-woven canes that cover the ancient wooden floor. 	The rooms on the ground floor are coeval with the building period of construction and only the windows were replaced in the nineteenth century. The staircase was instead inserted in 1945. Rooms were divided for residential use with partitions in the 80s of the 900s, making more complex the spaces reading. The windows were replaced during time with others in wood, while old shutters were kept. On the outside, the façade has recently been redone with a lime-based plaster, which is compatible with the underlying masonry.
GIULIO ROMANO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •It belongs to the 18th-19th centuries •It has documentary evidence through historic maps (i.e. Ranieri's map) 	It is part of the Mantova-historic centre.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On the outside the windows and the shadings in wood are characteristic elements of gothic lots of the 18th century. • The building is part of the building curtain of the eighteenth-century historic centre of Mantua. •The wall masonry it is testimony of the old use of raw bricks in the popular constructions in Mantova. • The false ceiling is still an interesting example, where preserved. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The presence of a wind tower and a double courtyard (internal and external) allowed for improved ventilation and lighting within the lot. • A portion of the building have been reconstructed after WWII and it is positioned alongside the internal courtyard. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Of great importance is the false ceiling system with hand-woven canes that cover the ancient wooden floor. 	The original nucleus of the building is internally recognizable by the presence of raw brick walls and reed false ceilings and a wooden roof with large single beams and wooden planks. The 50s wing has concrete floors with parquet that do not present any problems compared to the ancient part of the building; however, it would be appropriate to verify its structural compatibility in response to earthquakes
LEONARDO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •It belongs to the 16th century •It is part of the San Leonardo church complex •It has documentary evidence through historic maps (i.e. Ranieri's map) 	It is part of the Mantova-historic centre.	It is a residence, but also a community centre for the young catholic community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •There are numerous relevant elements: frescoes on walls and on wooden floors, brick arches in the walls, brick vaults. •The building is part of the San Leonardo church complex and it is directly connected to it. •The masonry, frescoes and floor decorations show an example of late renaissance art. 	Windows were retrofitted	The brick structure is really interesting in the cellar level. Decorated wooden floors and frescoed walls are also of high interest.	Although the building was modified in the 19th century, the difference between the old portion of the 16th century and the other is not perceptible today, except for the presence in many rooms of original decorated wooden ceilings and frescoes on the walls. In the rest of the building, plaster has covered the different layers, and the building has also been the subject of retrofit interventions in recent years. The basement also maintains its original configuration, which is not plastered for reasons of the presence of rising damp. The roof is not visible because it is not accessible, but we know that it has been recovered in recent years.
VESCOVILE	The building is recognized as a valuable example of notable architecture of the Mantuan city centre. It was built between 1776 and 1786, and belonged to the family of the Marquis Bianchi until 1823, when it was sold to the diocesan Curia and became a bishopric.	It is part of the Mantova-historic centre.	It houses the Diocesan Historical Archive, which has a rich documentary heritage relating to the diocese of Mantua.	The building is situated in the Piazza Sordello sightline. Notable elements are present in the building, demonstrating high quality of craftsmanship in decorations and in interiors.	Windows were retrofitted on the courtyard	The elegant façade is characterized by two powerful telamons on the sides of the entrance, which support a marble balcony. Inside, an imposing staircase leads to some beautiful rooms, frescoed by the eighteenth-century Mantuan painter Bazzani.	The building preserves its unique elements dating back to the 18th century. Inside, some changes have been made over time to accommodate the nuns who until recently lived on the residential floor - insertion of partitions, creation of bathrooms and kitchen rooms.

7. Conclusion

The work described in this report reflects what was done in the first 18 months of the HeriTACE project within the workpackage WP5 - Holistic and multi-scale renovation approach for heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods, T5.1 Cultural heritage analysis and value assessment of buildings and neighbourhoods - subtask T5.1.1 Cultural heritage analysis. The mentioned working group saw as fundamental the coordination and collaboration between partners expert in the heritage field –supported by governmental authorities responsible for the protection and preservation of cultural heritage– in four different EU countries.

Thanks to this collaborative effort, it was possible to test the *Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building*, developed by Politecnico di Milano, on case studies that were highly diverse in construction techniques, climate, and regulatory frameworks. The testing phase not only led to a well-calibrated version of the Summary Sheet but also enhanced mutual understanding of the varied case studies and associated archetypes.

In particular, the extensive dataset from Belgian cases proved particularly useful in highlighting both commonalities and divergences. Despite variations in typology and period—from the 19th to the early 20th century—these townhouses share common structural features: mixed masonry walls, wooden floors and roofs, and vaulted ceilings. Nevertheless, their conservation status, degree of authenticity, and functional transformations differ considerably. Some, like *Martens2*, *Koning*, and *Eyck*, retain much of their original layout and materials, while others, such as *Kuiper* and *Keizer*, have experienced significant loss of authenticity due to window replacements or interior renovations. Protection levels also vary: several properties (*Meers*, *Citadel*, *Muink*) fall within CHE-areas or are listed in official inventories, while others lack formal designation.

Most buildings have maintained their residential use—either as single-family homes (*Hert*, *Meers*) or modest dwellings (*Martens1*) – though some have undergone functional adaptation. Interventions primarily affected windows, annexes, and interior finishes, with differing impacts on heritage value. Some restorations were undertaken in line with historical models (*Brederode*, *Keizer*), while others introduced less sympathetic changes. Architecturally, neoclassical façades dominate, often preserving elaborate cornices, mouldings, and ironwork, contributing to the aesthetic and historic value of the urban fabric.

In the other HeriTACE partner countries, where the data set was smaller, intra-local comparisons were more limited.

The three Norwegian case studies, all built in log timber structure and clad both externally and internally with panelling, are located within an urban protection area (Level B / high antiquarian value). Despite this shared context, they represent three different types of townhouses: one with a courtyard, one with both a courtyard and a warehouse with a wharf, and one detached with a courtyard. Their various status of conservation reflects their functional histories - shifting from residential to other uses (e.g., a café in *Nedre1*, and 11 apartments in *Nedre2*) - and interventions, particularly in windows and interiors. Of the three, only *Nygata* retains part of its original external cladding, which remains protected.

In Estonia, the five case studies consist of three Stalinist-era brick apartment buildings and two Tallinn-type wooden apartment blocks, all dating from the first half of the 20th century. Although not formally protected, they are considered valuable as part of a typical *milieu*

area. Despite generally good structural condition, only *Pilve* retains original construction elements more intact, while the others have undergone extensive internal and external modifications, particularly with regard to windows and façades.

The Italian case studies reveal common values among the exclusively residential buildings (*Montanara* and *Giulio Romano*), which are situated in highly protected landscape zones. These cases show significant interventions, especially on rear façades and interior partitions. In contrast, the two mixed-use buildings (*Leonardo* and *Palazzo Vescovile*) present different dynamics: the former, used as a youth residence, has undergone subdivision but retains key interior features; the latter maintains a high-quality external condition, even in the courtyard, though the interiors have been moderately adapted during the 20th century.

Simultaneous use of the Summary Sheet across the Norwegian, Estonian, Italian, and Belgian case studies revealed striking commonalities despite geographic, constructive, material and cultural differences.

Indeed, in all contexts, a clear relationship emerges between construction typology, historical context, and long-term adaptation to residential or community use. Distinct structural preferences are evident: Norwegian log houses, Estonian wooden apartment blocks, Italian brick palazzetti, and Belgian neoclassical townhouses, often featuring timber elements in floors and roofs.

Across all groups, the presence of layered materials and hybrid techniques—such as reed-and-gypsum ceilings in Italy, clay-stub ceilings in Norway, or composite floors in Belgium—reflects local construction traditions and resourcefulness. Recent interventions are common but vary in their heritage impact. Norwegian and Estonian examples show substantial window replacements and retrofitting, affecting authenticity. Conversely, Italian and Belgian cases tend to preserve more original façades and interiors, including frescoes, decorative plasterwork, and staircases, even when subjected to adaptive reuse.

7.1. Key take-aways and Recommendations

The objective of this research was to develop a document for the preparations and analysis of townhouse case-study buildings and archetypes, covering aesthetic, architectural, historic, scientific, cultural, experiential, social values and beyond.

The testing phase of this document on a total of 23 cases (of which 11 Belgian cases, 3 Norwegian cases, 5 Estonian cases and 4 Italian cases) have supported the construction of a large dataset, useful to better define and understand archetypes peculiarities in different countries. As added value of this research work, part of the results obtained from this cultural heritage analysis and value assessment have already flowed into a separate deliverable (D5.4 Baseline Scenarios), dedicated precisely to the description of *pre-renovation baselines* for archetypes and heritage value scenarios, representing the situation of the townhouse *before a recent renovation* takes place, which may vary case by case.

In the next future, the results given by this work are thought to be useful to achieve the aim of the HeriTACE project in developing a holistic multidimensional approach, also defining new retrofit solutions and guidelines for retrofit intervention in different archetypes.

In particular, upcoming work is expected to start from the collected material to form a basis for defining a holistic set of heritage KPI for implementing contextualised and value-based renovation interventions in historic neighbourhoods with similar levels of cultural

importance and protection, i.e. pre-renovation baseline scenarios (more information on that will be provided in Deliverable 5.5).

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Project Deliverables reference list

D2.1 Building envelope characteristics.

D2.2 Energy conservation measures inventory. <https://zenodo.org/records/15364987>

D3.1 HVAC concepts for heritage buildings. <https://zenodo.org/records/15365094>

D5.1 Case-study selection at building and neighbourhood levels. <https://zenodo.org/records/15365504>

D4.1 R²ES-based energy supply concepts for heritage buildings in historical neighbourhoods.

D5.1 Case-study selection at building and neighbourhood levels. <https://zenodo.org/records/15365504>

D5.2 Cultural heritage analysis and value assessment.

D5.3 Cultural heritage building user and owner perspectives.

D5.4 Baseline scenarios

D5.5 Map of KPI

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Standards

EN 16095:2012. Conservation of cultural property - Condition recording for movable cultural heritage.

EN 16096:2012. Conservation of cultural property - Condition survey and report of built cultural heritage.

EN 16883:2017. Conservation of cultural heritage - Guidelines for improving the energy performance of historic buildings.

EN 15898:2011. Conservation of cultural property - Main general terms and definitions.

Annex

Annex 1 - Documents

Summary Sheet for the Survey of a Historic Building (public access) - doi: **10.5281/zenodo.15753722**

Summary Sheet testing (private access only for HeriTACE partners):

- Belgian case studies - doi: **10.5281/zenodo.15755749**
- Norwegian case studies - doi: **10.5281/zenodo.15756099**
- Estonian case studies - doi: **10.5281/zenodo.15755900**
- Italian case studies - doi: **10.5281/zenodo.15755676**

Annex 2– Examples of allowable measures per heritage value categories

Table 13: Summary of allowable measures at building component level considering cultural heritage value categories.

		Heritage value category				
		Category 0: Only conservation measures allowed	Category 1: Low impact measures allowed	Category 2: Medium impact measures allowed	Category 3: High impact measures allowed	Category 4: Any measures allowed
Restrictions						
Exterior wall	Finishing layer	Restoring	Reintegrating the existing / repainting	New compatible plaster	New compatible plaster	New plaster also changing color and texture
	Handling of damages	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them
	Detailing	Preserve	Repair	Preserve or copy	Replace with similar	New detailing
	Thermal insulation	Not allowed	Not allowed	Allowed if proportions kept	Allowed if proportions similar	Allowed without restrictions
Interior wall	Finishing layer	Restoring	Repainting	New compatible plaster	New compatible plaster	New plaster also changing colour and texture
	Handling of damages	Local repair of damaged plaster, replacement of rotten wooden details using traditional techniques	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them with medium impact techniques	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them	Intervening on damage causes to reduce them also with new techniques
	Detailing	Preserve	Repair and preserve	Repair, preserve or copy	Replace with similar	New detailing
	Thermal insulation	Not allowed	Allowed if not with decorations	Allowed if proportions kept	Allowed if proportions similar	Allowed without restrictions
Windows	Frame	Restoring rotten woodwork using traditional techniques	Replacing rotten woodwork using traditional techniques	Replacing damaged frames with similar new one	Replacing non-original or non-valuable windows with new windows (same material and layout as the original)	Replacement of existing windows with new windows (different material, layout, detailing and glazing from original)

	Finishing	Restoring and integrating with same colour type and tone	Repainting with same colour type and tone	Same colour tone	New colour	New colour and finishing type
	Profiles and detailing	Keep and restore	Repair	Preserve or copy	Replace with similar	New detailing
	Energy-improvement and glazing	No improvement, replacing broken glass using traditional techniques	Installing gaskets, solar film, interior shutters	Replacing single glass with double glazing or vacuum glass; installing front window if no valuable interior	New energy-efficient windows	New energy-efficient windows
Roof	Covering material	Repainting old roof cover, substituting damaged parts with identical ones to ensure watertightness of the roof	Repair and replace old roof cover with same material and detailing	Replace old roof cover with material with similar to original	Replace with new material used on similar houses in neighbourhood	Replacement roof with different material, colour and detailing, changing the roofscape
	Load-bearing constructions	Reintegrating broken elements using traditional techniques	Replace broken elements with same material, preserving undamaged parts	Change the load-bearing structure in some parts to convert attic to living space	Add new roof elements (roof windows, dormers etc)	Replace all the load-bearing construction with new solution
	Thermal insulation	Not allowed?	Add additional loose insulation layer to attic floor	Add suitable insulation between existing rafters	Install suitable roof insulation layers while keeping the external appearance of the roof	Install thermal insulation according to modern practices
	PV-panels	Not allowed	Allowed if integrated and not visible from neighbourhood	Allowed to courtyard side of the house, not visible from street	Allowed	Allowed
	Windows or dormers	Not allowed	Only for fire safety measures	Allowed if not visible from street or similar solutions to houses in	Allowed if main character of the house is kept	Allowed

			neighbourhood			
Chimney	Replaster and repair damages	Replaster and repair damages	Replace damaged upper parts using similar materials	Replace the chimney, but keep similar external appearance	Replace the chimney using modern materials	Remove chimney if not needed anymore
Interior elements	Interior elements	Preserve original details	Repair	Preserve or copy	Replace interior doors with new ones	Replace interior doors with new ones
	Paint or finishing	Conservating finishes, often overpainting is not allowed in same parts. Renewing floor finishing.	Overpaint surfaces with same colour.	Replace finishing layers with new material.	Replace finishing layers with new material.	Replace finishing layers with new material.
	Technical systems	Recovery existing systems and replacing faulty technical systems with similar ones.	Replace surface mounted technical systems with suitable modern ones.	Replace or add new technical systems	Replace or add new technical systems	Replace or add new technical systems
	Room plan	Keep original room plan	Restore original room plan if changed later	Modifications to create modern washrooms	Change room planning	Change room planning